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Advanced Remote Sensing and In Situ Observations of Aerosols, Clouds, and Precipitation to Improve Process Understanding of the Arctic Climate System

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Wolken und Niederschlag sind Schlüsselkomponenten des arktischen Klimasystems, aber die Prozesse der Wolken- und Niederschlagsbildung sind nicht ausreichend verstanden, was zu Problemen bei der Abschätzung führt, wie sich die Arktis und das globale Klimasystem als Folge einer Klimaerwärmung verändern werden.

In dieser Arbeit werden verschiedene Ansätze vorgestellt, um unsere Beobachtungsmöglichkeiten von Wolken und Niederschlag mit Fernerkundung wie Wolkenradargeräten, in situ Beobachtungen und Satellitenprodukten zu verbessern. Die verbesserten Beobachtungsmethoden werden angewendet, um das Verständnis von Wolken und Niederschlagsprozessen zu verbessern. Der Schwerpunkt liegt auf der Arktis, aber viele der Ergebnisse sind auch auf andere Regionen übertragbar.

Diese kumulative Habilitationsschrift basiert auf zehn Veröffentlichungen, die in drei Hauptthemen gruppiert sind. Die im ersten Thema *Verbesserung der Messungen von Wolken und Niederschlag* vorgestellten Studien tragen zur allgemeinen Verbesserung unserer Beobachtungsmöglichkeiten bei. Sie befassen sich mit der Kalibrierung von Wolkenradaren, diskutieren Unsicherheitsquellen bei inversen Optimal Estimation Retrievals und stellen eine neuartige in situ Schneefallkamera vor, um besondere Merkmale der Niederschlagsbildung zu erkennen und qualitativ hochwertige Datensätze für inverse Retrievalverfahren zu erhalten.

Die im zweiten Thema *Beobachtung der Aerosol-Wolken-Wechselwirkung* vorgestellten Veröffentlichungen untersuchen die Wechselwirkungen zwischen Aerosolpartikeln und Wolken an der Nordküste Alaskas. Da es sich um eine wenig anthropogen beeinflusste Umgebung mit wenigen menschlich verursachten Aerosolquellen handelt, können die Auswirkungen der Emissionen aus dem Prudhoe Bay Ölfeld auf die Wolken direkt beobachtet werden. Zu diesem Zweck werden Flugzeug- und Satellitenbeobachtungen ausgewertet.

Das dritte Thema *Zum Verständnis des Bereifungs-Prozesses* befasst sich mit dem Bereifungsprozess und stellt verschiedene Methoden zur Quantifizierung von Bereifung mithilfe von Fernerkundung und in situ Beobachtungen vor. Diese Methoden werden verwendet, um zu untersuchen, wie Bereifung die räumliche Variabilität von Mischphasenwolken verändert. Schließlich wird der Beitrag von Bereifung zur sekundären Eisproduktion abgeschätzt.

Die in dieser Arbeit entwickelten Methoden bilden die Grundlage für zukünftige Studien, die dazu beitragen werden, die Rolle von Wolken und Niederschlag im arktischen Klimasystem weiter zu untersuchen.

Abstract

Maahn, Maximilian

Advanced Remote Sensing and In Situ Observations of Aerosols, Clouds, and Precipitation to Improve Process Understanding of the Arctic Climate System

Leipzig University, Habilitation Thesis

303 pages, 269 references, 19 figures, 1 table

Clouds and precipitation are key components of the Arctic climate system, but the processes of cloud and precipitation formation are not well understood, leading to problems in our ability to estimate how the Arctic and the global climate system will change in a warming climate.

In this thesis, I present different approaches to improve our observational capabilities for clouds and precipitation. For this, remote sensing with cloud radars, in situ observations, and satellite products are used. The improved observational methods are applied with the goal to improve the understanding of clouds and precipitation processes. The main focus is on Arctic regions, but many of the results are also applicable to other regions.

This cumulative habilitation thesis consists of ten papers grouped into three key topics. The studies presented in the first topic *Improving measurements of clouds and precipitation* contribute to the general improvement of our observational capabilities. They deal with the evaluation of cloud radar calibration, discuss sources of uncertainty in inverse Optimal Estimation retrievals, and introduce a novel in situ snow camera to identify precipitation formation fingerprints and obtain high quality prior data sets for inverse retrievals.

The two papers presented in the second topic *Observing aerosol-cloud interaction* investigate aerosol-cloud interactions on the North Slope of Alaska. As this is a pristine environment with few anthropogenic aerosol sources, the effect of emissions associated with the Prudhoe Bay oil field on clouds can be directly observed. Airborne and satellite observations are used for this purpose.

In the third topic *Understanding the riming process*, the focus is on the riming process and various methods for quantifying riming using remote sensing and in situ observations are presented. These methods are used to investigate how riming modifies the spatial variability of mixed-phase clouds. Finally, the contribution of riming to secondary ice production is assessed.

The methods developed in this thesis provide a foundation for many future studies that will help unravel the role of clouds and precipitation in the Arctic climate system.

List of Included Papers

The following papers, referred to in the text by their Roman numerals I to X and grouped into three main topics, are synthesized in this cumulative habilitation thesis. Author contributions are copied from the papers when available. Reprints have been made with permission from the publishers.

Improving measurements of clouds and precipitation

- Paper I Maahn, M., Hoffmann, F., Shupe, M. D., de Boer, G., Matrosov, S. Y., and Luke, E. P.: Can Liquid Cloud Microphysical Processes Be Used for Vertically Pointing Cloud Radar Calibration?, *Atmos. Meas. Tech.*, 12, 3151–3171, doi:[10.5194/amt-12-3151-2019](https://doi.org/10.5194/amt-12-3151-2019), 2019
Author contributions: M. Maahn developed the methodology, ran the model, analyzed the data, and drafted the manuscript. F. Hoffmann developed and adapted the model. M. Shupe provided the phase classification. All authors contributed to the methodology, the interpretation of the results, and the editing of the paper.
- Paper II Maahn, M., Turner, D. D., Löhnert, U., Posselt, D. J., Ebell, K., Mace, G. G., and Comstock, J. M.: Optimal Estimation Retrievals and Their Uncertainties: What Every Atmospheric Scientist Should Know, *Bull. Am. Meteorol. Soc.*, 101, E1512–E1523, doi:[10.1175/BAMS-D-19-0027.1](https://doi.org/10.1175/BAMS-D-19-0027.1), 2020
Author contributions: The study was designed by M. Maahn and D. Turner with contributions from all authors. M. Maahn developed the Python library, wrote the supporting Jupyter Notebooks, analyzed the examples cases, did all but one figure, and drafted the majority of the manuscript. D. Turner created Figure 1 and drafted the introduction. All authors reviewed and edited the draft.
- Paper III Maahn, M., Moisseev, D., Steinke, I., Maherndl, N., and Shupe, M. D.: Introducing the Video In Situ Snowfall Sensor (VISSS), *Atmos. Meas. Tech.*, 17, 899–919, doi:[10.5194/amt-17-899-2024](https://doi.org/10.5194/amt-17-899-2024), 2024
Author contributions: M. Maahn acquired funding, developed the instrument, processed the VISSS data, analyzed the data of the case study, and wrote the manuscript. D. Moisseev processed PIP and Parsivel data and contributed to data analysis. N. Maherndl and I. Steinke contributed to instrument calibration and particle tracking development, respectively. M. Shupe supported funding acquisition and was responsible for the VISSS deployment at MOSAiC. All authors reviewed and edited the draft.

Observing aerosol-cloud interaction

- Paper IV Maahn, M., de Boer, G., Creamean, J. M., Feingold, G., McFarquhar, G. M., Wu, W., and Mei, F.: The Observed Influence of Local Anthropogenic Pollution on Northern Alaskan Cloud Properties, *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 17, 14 709–14 726, doi:[10.5194/acp-17-14709-2017](https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-17-14709-2017), 2017
Author contributions: The study was designed by M. Maahn and G. de Boer with contributions from all authors. M. Maahn analyzed the data, created the figures, and drafted the manuscript. G. de Boer acquired funding. J. Creamean supported the analysis of the aerosol data, G. Feingold supported quantifying the aerosol effects. G. McFarquhar, W. Wu, and F. Mei processed in situ cloud observations and assisted with their use. All authors reviewed and edited the draft.
- Paper V Maahn, M., Goren, T., Shupe, M. D., and de Boer, G.: Liquid Containing Clouds at the North Slope of Alaska Demonstrate Sensitivity to Local Industrial Aerosol Emissions, *Geophys. Res. Lett.*, 48, e2021GL094 307, doi:[10.1029/2021GL094307](https://doi.org/10.1029/2021GL094307), 2021
Author contributions: The study was designed by M. Maahn with contributions from all authors. M. Maahn analyzed the data, created the figures, and drafted the manuscript. T. Goren supported the MODIS data analysis. G. de Boer acquired funding. G. de Boer and M. Shupe supported the interpretation of the results. All authors reviewed and edited the draft.

Understanding the riming process

- Paper VI Vogl, T., Maahn, M., Kneifel, S., Schimmel, W., Moisseev, D., and Kalesse-Los, H.: Using Artificial Neural Networks to Predict Riming from Doppler Cloud Radar Observations, *Atmos. Meas. Tech.*, 15, 365–381, doi:[10.5194/amt-15-365-2022](https://doi.org/10.5194/amt-15-365-2022), 2022
Author contributions: The method was developed by T. Vogl, M. Maahn, and H. Kalesse-Los with contributions by all co-authors. S. Kneifel provided the RIPEXpol data set, D. Moisseev the in situ data for the BA ECC data set, and M. Maahn the in situ data for the Leipzig data set. T. Vogl performed data visualization and analysis, with help from all co-authors. The text was written by T. Vogl and reviewed by all co-authors.
- Paper VII Maherndl, N., Maahn, M., Tridon, F., Leinonen, J., Ori, D., and Kneifel, S.: A Riming-Dependent Parameterization of Scattering by Snowflakes Using the Self-Similar Rayleigh–Gans Approximation, *Q. J. R. Meteorolog. Soc.*, 149, 3562–3581, doi:[10.1002/qj.4573](https://doi.org/10.1002/qj.4573), 2023
Author contributions: N. Maherndl: conceptualization; formal analysis; methodology; visualization; writing – original draft; writing – review and editing. M. Maahn: conceptualization; funding acquisition; supervision; writing – review and editing. F. Tridon: conceptualization; software; writing – review and editing. J. Leinonen: software; writing – review and editing. D. Ori: software; writing – review and editing. S. Kneifel: conceptualization; writing – review and editing.

Paper VIII Maherndl, N., Moser, M., Lucke, J., Mech, M., Risse, N., Schirmacher, I., and Maahn, M.: Quantifying Riming from Airborne Data during the HALO-(AC)³ Campaign, *Atmos. Meas. Tech.*, 17, 1475–1495, doi:[10.5194/amt-17-1475-2024](https://doi.org/10.5194/amt-17-1475-2024), 2024a

Author contributions: N. Maherndl developed the described methods to quantify riming, analyzed and plotted the data, and wrote the paper. M. Maahn acquired funding and supervised the research project. M. Moser collected and processed CDP, CIP, and PIP data and provided combined size distributions. J. Lucke collected and processed Nevzorov probe data. M. Mech and N. Risse collected and processed MiRAC-A data and retrieved the LWP product. M. Mech, N. Risse, and I. Schirmacher collected and processed AMALi data and retrieved the CTH product. All authors reviewed and edited the draft.

Paper IX Maherndl, N., Moser, M., Schirmacher, I., Bansemer, A., Lucke, J., Voigt, C., and Maahn, M.: How Does Riming Influence the Observed Spatial Variability of Ice Water in Mixed-Phase Clouds?, *EGUsph.* (in review for ACP), pp. 1–38, doi:[10.5194/egusphere-2024-1214](https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-2024-1214), 2024b

Author contributions: N. Maherndl conceptualized the study, analyzed and plotted the data, and wrote the paper. M. Maahn contributed to the concept, acquired funding, and supervised the research project. M. Moser and C. Voigt collected and processed CDP, CIP, and PIP data during HALO-(AC)³ and provided combined size distributions. J. Lucke collected and processed Nevzorov probe data during HALO-(AC)³. I. Schirmacher collected and processed AMALi data during HALO-(AC)³ and retrieved the CTH product. A. Bansemer collected and processed CDP, Fast-CDP, 2D-S, and HVPS-3 data during IMPACTS and provided combined size distributions. All authors reviewed and edited the draft.

Paper X Luke, E. P., Yang, F., Kollias, P., Vogelmann, A. M., and Maahn, M.: New Insights into Ice Multiplication Using Remote-Sensing Observations of Slightly Supercooled Mixed-Phase Clouds in the Arctic, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.*, 118, doi:[10.1073/pnas.2021387118](https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2021387118), 2021

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In loving memory of Angelika
* 24.07.1954 † 13.09.2024

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Motivation

The Arctic has been warming two to three times faster than the rest of the Earth. This warming has led to dramatic changes in the environment, affecting permafrost (Schuur et al., 2022), sea ice (Eayrs et al., 2021), surface albedo (Zhang et al., 2019), the water cycle (Koutsoyiannis, 2020), and ecosystems (Rixen et al., 2022). In addition, more extreme changes are expected in the future (IPCC, 2021). Many of these processes are embedded in positive feedback mechanisms leading to further warming of the Arctic, termed Arctic amplification (Serreze and Francis, 2006; Wendisch et al., 2023).

The changing Arctic climate has a significant impact on clouds, as they are closely linked to environmental conditions such as sea ice cover (Kay and Gettelman, 2009; Morrison et al., 2018; Alkama et al., 2020; Stapf et al., 2020; Lim et al., 2021), aerosol concentrations (Zhao and Garrett, 2015; Solomon et al., 2018; Carlsen and David, 2022), and atmospheric stability (Murray-Watson and Gryspeerdt, 2022; Chechin et al., 2023). Precipitation is formed in clouds and is thus also impacted by changing sea ice cover (Kopec et al., 2016), and aerosol properties (Lohmann et al., 2003). Through dynamic linkages, a warming Arctic is suspected to alter mid-latitude precipitation (Cohen et al., 2020; Bailey et al., 2021). In a warming Arctic climate, the fraction of liquid hydrometeors in clouds (Tsushima et al., 2006) and precipitation (Screen and Simmonds, 2012; Bintanja and Andry, 2017) is expected to increase, with effects on the radiative budget (Sledd and L'Ecuyer, 2021). This explains the important role of clouds and precipitation in feedback mechanisms that have been proposed to amplify global warming in the Arctic, such as the albedo feedback (Hall, 2004) and the cloud radiative feedback (Middlemas et al., 2020). Precipitation amounts and extreme events, including heavy snowfall, are also assumed to increase (Krasting et al., 2013; Quante et al., 2021), but the exact magnitudes are subject to large uncertainties (Lopez-Cantu et al., 2020) due to the challenges associated with realistically representing clouds in atmospheric models.

Arctic low-level clouds are typically mixed-phase, i. e., consisting of supercooled liquid water droplets and ice particles (Morrison et al., 2012). Mixed-phase clouds can persist for several days, but the exact pathways by which ice particles, liquid droplets, and cloud dynamics maintain mixed-phase clouds, although supercooled liquid water should preferably evaporate in the presence of ice particles, are not well understood (Wegener, 1911; Bergeron, 1935; Findeisen, 1938). Aerosols particles are necessary for cloud formation, but it is unclear how cloud condensation nuclei (CCN) and ice nucleating particles (INP) interact and change cloud properties and evolution (Solomon et al., 2018; Radenz et al., 2021). Precipitation formation also plays a critical role in cloud evolution and lifetime by removing condensate from the atmosphere, but there are still significant uncertainties in the understanding of water

vapor deposition processes on ice particles (Fukuta and Takahashi, 1999; Westbrook et al., 2008; Field et al., 2008), ice particle aggregation (Passarelli and Srivastava, 1979; Westbrook et al., 2004; Chellini and Kneifel, 2024), and droplet riming on ice particles (Böhm, 1994; Leinonen and Szyrmer, 2015). In addition, these processes mostly concern small scales, usually less than the grid size of atmospheric models so that even the most advanced microphysical schemes of models have to rely heavily on parameterizations (Hashino and Tripoli, 2007; Morrison and Milbrandt, 2014; Diehl and Grützun, 2018). Therefore, the *“representation of microphysical processes in models continues to pose a major challenge”* (Morrison et al., 2020) and substantial advances in observational techniques and retrieval methods are needed (Morrison et al., 2020).

Observations of aerosols, clouds, and precipitation are challenging because a wide range of spatial scales need to be considered and clouds and precipitation are constantly evolving in time. Also, the principle of most instruments is to measure indirectly and they are not really observing the quantities required in the end. A cloud radar measures amplitude and phase shift of a reflected microwave signal, but not ice water content (*IWC*) or precipitation rate (e. g., Liu and Illingworth, 2000). An optical disdrometer does not measure the required size of individual hydrometeors, instead it detects the shadow of the particle on a detector (e. g., Newman et al., 2009; Baumgardner et al., 2017). The satellite instrument MODIS (Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer) does not measure the effective radius of the cloud droplet size distribution (DSD), but the number and frequency of photons emitted by the cloud (e. g., Platnick et al., 2003). Thus, the required specific information have to be extracted from the observations that are typically only partially related to the atmospheric variables of interest. In addition, the instruments have fundamental limitations and require e. g., a minimal optical thickness of a cloud, a minimal size of a hydrometeor, or a maximal sun zenith angle to provide the desired information. Therefore, we urgently need retrievals that can combine the observations—given their limitations—with prior information to provide the atmospheric variables of interest. These retrievals can be anything from a simple linear regression to a sophisticated inverse model based on Bayes’ theorem (e. g., Rodgers, 2000). Common to all of the retrievals is that they all make—sometimes less, sometimes more explicit—assumptions about the problem to be observed. This may be the typical shape and size distribution of ice particles at a given *IWC* for a radar (e. g., Lu et al., 2015), the orientation of a falling ice particle aggregate for a disdrometer (e. g., Jiang et al., 2017), or the concentration of water vapor above the cloud for MODIS (e. g., Platnick et al., 2001). This means that part of the answer often has to be known in advance. And it is not uncommon that these assumptions are forgotten during the data analysis, which can result in misinterpretations of the measurements. Therefore, it can be extremely challenging to develop observing systems with low uncertainties that can provide the desired insight into the microphysical processes within clouds and precipitation.

1.2 Processes related to aerosols, clouds and precipitation

Clouds interact with the Arctic environment in a variety of ways. They form precipitation* typically in the form of snowfall which—if the snow reaches the ground—impacts surface albedo (Zhang et al., 2019), the hydrological cycle (Yongjian et al., 2020), sea ice (Perovich et al., 2017), road safety (Abohassan et al., 2021), and ecology

*Precipitation can be defined either as hydrometeors that are large enough to fall due to gravity or as the amount of water (frozen or liquid) that has fallen over a certain period of time (AMS, 2024). In this thesis, the former definition is used.

(Rixen et al., 2022). Mixed-phase clouds are particularly relevant to the Arctic because they are an important modulator of the climate system’s radiation budget and can persist over several days (Morrison et al., 2012). Depending on the season, they can lead to both net cooling (summer) and warming (winter) of the Arctic surface (Intrieri et al., 2002; Shupe and Intrieri, 2004; Wendisch et al., 2023).

In mixed-phase clouds*, both CCN and—except for temperatures colder than $-38\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ —INP are required to form droplets and ice particles, respectively. Due to the limited number of sources, the Arctic is typically characterized by relatively low numbers of CCN (Mauritsen et al., 2011) and INP (Schrod et al., 2020). Therefore, long-range transport of aerosol particles from lower latitudes in winter and early spring (Arctic haze) and episodic forest fires in summer can lead to higher aerosol concentrations (Shaw, 1995; Law and Stohl, 2007), which modify the properties of liquid water and mixed-phase clouds (Garrett et al., 2004; McFarquhar et al., 2011; Jackson et al., 2012; Zamora et al., 2016). For liquid water clouds, this has been shown to affect cloud albedo, lifetime, and longwave emissivity (Twomey, 1976; Albrecht, 1989; Garrett and Zhao, 2006), and it is assumed that mixed-phase clouds are generally affected similarly. One way to study aerosol-cloud interaction (ACI) in the Arctic is to use the seasonal cycle of Arctic aerosol properties, which provides opportunities to understand ACI (Garrett and Zhao, 2006; Zamora et al., 2017; Coopman et al., 2018; Zieger et al., 2023). One common definition used to quantify ACI is

$$ACI = \frac{1}{3} \frac{d \log_{10} N_{\text{tot}}}{d \log_{10} N_a} \quad (1.1)$$

with N_{tot} the number concentration of cloud droplets and N_a the number concentration of aerosol particles (Feingold et al., 2001; McComiskey et al., 2009). However, the quantification of ACI is complicated by the conflation of ACI effects with meteorological drivers such as changes in moisture and dynamics, which severely limits the understanding of how clouds containing liquid water interact with CCN (Feingold et al., 2016; Gryspeerd et al., 2016; Sena et al., 2016; Rosenfeld et al., 2019).

The effects of INP on cloud precipitation properties are even more unclear than for CCN (Kanji et al., 2017; Burrows et al., 2022; Tan et al., 2022). While there have been aircraft campaigns showing how liquid water clouds can be glaciated by INP seeding (Bruitjes, 1999; Henneberger et al., 2023), it is still debated to what extent INP seeding modifies clouds and precipitation (Flossmann et al., 2019). In the temperature range between $-10\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, the number of INP is small (DeMott et al., 2010), but measured ice particle number concentrations are often orders of magnitude larger than what would be expected from primary ice production alone (Korolev and Leisner, 2020), indicating secondary ice production (SIP). This may indicate that INP concentrations only have a secondary effect on clouds and that SIP is more important (Zhao and Liu, 2022). While it is recognized that SIP is a fundamental cloud microphysical process that may explain the gap between INP and ice particle concentrations, it is unclear both qualitatively and quantitatively which cloud processes contribute to SIP (Field et al., 2017; Korolev and Leisner, 2020). Rime splintering (Hallett and Mossop, 1974) has been assumed to be a relevant SIP process and is often the only one implemented in atmospheric models (e. g., Morrison et al., 2005). However, recent studies have suggested (Lauber et al., 2018; Keinert et al., 2020) that droplet freezing fragmentation (Koenig, 1965) may also be a relevant process and Seidel et al. (2024) have failed to reproduce the results of Hallett and Mossop (1974).

*This paragraph has been adapted from Paper V (Maahn et al., 2021)

After nucleation, precipitation is typically formed by ice-phase processes (Mülmenstädt et al., 2015) in the Arctic, but the details of precipitation formation processes are unclear: Water vapor deposition describes the growth of ice particles in a supersaturated environment, but how the ability of a water vapor molecule to adhere to an ice particle depends on particle shape is not yet clear (Fukuta and Takahashi, 1999; Westbrook et al., 2008; Field et al., 2008). Aggregation combines individual ice particles into complex snow crystals, but the collision efficiency for the particles is not well understood (Passarelli and Srivastava, 1979; Westbrook et al., 2004; Chellini and Kneifel, 2024). The same is true for riming, which describes the freezing of small droplets into ice particles (Böhm, 1994; Leinonen and Szyrmer, 2015). It is also not known how these different precipitation formation processes contribute relatively to total snowfall, and results for e. g., riming vary widely (Harimaya and Sato, 1989; Kneifel and Moisseev, 2020; Waitz et al., 2021). This lack of process understanding also limits the quantification of cloud evolution processes because snowfall removes water from the atmosphere.

1.3 Remote sensing observations

Remote sensing observations are used to monitor clouds and precipitation. Because of their profiling capabilities, cloud radars (Radio Detection and Ranging) are one of the most important tools for ground-based remote sensing. A radar transmits radio pulses and receives the backscattered signal from objects in the atmosphere, such as hydrometers. For cloud radars, observations are typically made at Ka-band (35 GHz) or W-band (94 GHz) because these wavelengths provide an optimal balance of sensitivity and usable range. Cloud radars are operated on the ground (Kollias et al., 2016; Küchler et al., 2017), on aircraft (Mech et al., 2014; Li et al., 2016; Mech et al., 2019), and in space (Stephens et al., 2002; Wehr et al., 2023). Typically, cloud radars are operated collocated with other remote sensing instruments such as lidars and microwave radiometers to take advantage of synergistic effects and to determine e. g., thermodynamic phase (Illingworth et al., 2007; Delanoë and Hogan, 2010; Stevens et al., 2019). Studies using cloud radars have investigated a wide range of topics such as precipitation formation (Acquistapace et al., 2019; Kneifel and Moisseev, 2020), entrainment (Moninger and Kropfli, 1987; Albrecht et al., 2016), spatial variability (Kogan et al., 2005; Richter et al., 2007; Radtke et al., 2022), model evaluation (Heinze et al., 2017; Ori et al., 2020), cloud microphysics (Chase et al., 2021; Chellini and Kneifel, 2024) and cloud macrophysical properties (Mages et al., 2023; Wendisch et al., 2024).

The received signal depends strongly on the backscattering cross section (σ_B) of a single hydrometeor. For snow and ice particles, estimating σ_B is challenging because, at least for cloud radar, they are often too large to assume the validity of Rayleigh scattering (Lord Rayleigh, 1899; Young, 1981) and σ_B depends on particle size, shape, and density (Kneifel et al., 2020). The most sophisticated method for estimating σ_B is the Discrete Dipole Approximation method (DDA, DeVoe, 1964, 1965). DDA can handle complex particle shapes, but this requires a detailed description of the ice distribution of the modeled particles, e. g., from an aggregation model (Westbrook et al., 2004). DDA is computationally expensive, so it is common to use databases to store the results (Liu, 2008; Petty and Huang, 2010; Tyynelä et al., 2011, 2014). Having only a certain number of particles with discrete properties makes it difficult to represent continuous property changes caused by e. g., riming.

Another approach targets the bulk backscattering cross section rather than trying to estimate the scattering properties of individual particles. The soft sphere approach (Bohren and Battan, 1980; Liu, 2004) assumes that the particles have a spherical or ellipsoidal shape so that the scattering properties can be estimated using Mie theory (Mie, 1908; Bohren and Huffman, 1983) or the T-Matrix method (Waterman, 1965; Mishchenko, 2000), respectively, and adjust the mean density of the particle to account for variability in particle mass or shape. While these methods are simple to apply, they have been found to introduce biases (Kneifel et al., 2020). By combining the assumption that snow crystals are fractal with the Gans (Gans, 1912) extension of Rayleigh theory, Hogan et al. (2012) and Hogan and Westbrook (2014) developed the Self-Similar Rayleigh Gans Approximation (SSRGA), which compares better to DDA calculations than the soft sphere approach. However, polarization effects cannot be modeled with SSRGA, and assumptions about the mass distribution within the particle do not account for riming. In summary, a computationally efficient and accurate method for estimating bulk scattering properties over a wide range of conditions is still lacking.

Assuming a single type of hydrometeor, the radar reflectivity $\tilde{\eta}$ can be estimated with

$$\tilde{\eta} = \int_0^{\infty} N(D) \cdot \sigma_B(D) dD \quad (1.2)$$

where D is the particle size, $N(D)$ is the particle number distribution. In atmospheric science, $\tilde{\eta}$ is typically expressed in terms of the equivalent radar reflectivity factor

$$Z_e = \frac{\lambda^4}{|K_w|^2 \pi^5} \tilde{\eta} \quad (1.3)$$

where λ is the radar wavelength and $|K_w|^2$ is the dielectric constant. Since the phase of the observed hydrometeors is usually unknown, it is convention to use the $|K_w|^2$ value for liquid water (Rinehart, 1991). Today, cloud radars measure a spectrum of radar reflectivity as a function of Doppler velocity. From this, variables such as mean Doppler velocity, Doppler spectrum width, and skewness can be derived. Polarimetric radars can receive and sometimes transmit polarized radiation, giving additional insight into hydrometeor properties, but this is beyond the scope of this study.

Because radar instruments observe the atmosphere indirectly, retrievals are required to convert the observations to atmospheric quantities such as *IWC* or snowfall rate (*SR*). The easiest form is to use a simple power law with empirical constants to convert Z_e to *IWC* or *SR* (Noh et al., 2006; Kulie and Bennartz, 2009; Souverijns et al., 2017). However, Z_e and *IWC* (and *SR*) are affected differently by particle shape, mass, and size. Thus, *IWC* (and *SR*) cannot be constrained by Z_e alone, and retrieval results have significant uncertainties, as can be seen from the variability of published Z_e -*IWC* relations (Figure 1.1). Previous studies have attempted to partially overcome this issue by including additional information such as temperature (Wood and L'Ecuyer, 2021), ground-based in situ observations (Cooper et al., 2017), spectral radar observations (Maahn et al., 2015; Maahn and Löhnert, 2017), multi-wavelength radar observations (Kneifel et al., 2011), or polarimetric measurements (Oue et al., 2018) using inverse retrieval methods (see Section 1.5).

FIGURE 1.1: Comparison of various empirical (solid) and theoretical (dashed) $Z_e - IWC$ relations. Figure by Liu and Illingworth (2000). ©American Meteorological Society. Used with permission.

1.4 In situ observations

In situ observations* of clouds and precipitation typically focus on properties related to small scales such as single particle properties. There is a wide variety of airborne and ground-based in situ sensors with different measurement techniques. For observations of cloud and precipitation properties, most instruments are based on optical principles. One example is the group of particle imagers, which record shadow images of particles illuminated from behind (Figure 1.2) and are operated on aircraft (Baumgardner et al., 2011; Wendisch and Brenguier, 2013; Schnaiter et al., 2018) and on the ground (Newman et al., 2009; Garrett et al., 2012). For frozen hydrometeors, this allows the fingerprints of individual snowfall formation processes to be identified and provides detailed information on particle size, shape and, for some ground-based imagers, fall velocity. These data have been used to characterize particle mass or density (Tiira et al., 2016; von Lerber et al., 2017; Pettersen et al., 2020; Leinonen et al., 2021; Vázquez-Martín et al., 2021a; Fitch and Garrett, 2022), particle shape (Nurzyńska et al., 2013; Grazioli et al., 2014; Praz et al., 2017; Hicks and Notaroš, 2019; Leinonen and Berne, 2020; Del Guasta, 2022), size distributions (Kulie et al., 2021), snowfall formation (Grazioli et al., 2017; Moisseev et al., 2017; Dunnavan et al., 2019; Pasquier et al., 2023), sedimentation velocity and turbulence of hydrometeors (Garrett et al., 2012; Garrett and Yuter, 2014; Li et al., 2021; Vázquez-Martín et al., 2021b; Takami et al., 2022), and for model evaluation (Vignon et al., 2019). In combination with ground-based remote sensing, in situ snowfall data have been used to validate or interpret remote sensing observations (Gergely and Garrett, 2016; Mascio and Mace, 2017; Li et al., 2018; Matrosov et al., 2020), to develop joint radar in situ retrievals (Cooper et al., 2017, 2022), and to train remote sensing retrievals (Maahn et al., 2015; Huang et al., 2015; Vogl et al., 2022).

The exponential nature of the size distributions of hydrometeors leads to a specialization of in situ instruments to certain size ranges. Small particles are frequently abundant, so sampling volumes are typically small to allow for a high optical resolution (e. g., Cloud Imaging Probe). Larger particles are rare, so a larger sampling

*This paragraph has been adapted from Paper III (Maahn et al., 2024)

FIGURE 1.2: Sketch of the basic principle of particle imaging with optical instruments. Figure by Maherndl (2024) based on Wendisch and Brenguier (2013).

volume is required to obtain meaningful statistics limiting the optical resolution (e. g., 2D precipitation probe). For airborne observations, this means that a size distribution is typically composed of measurements from multiple instruments, and discontinuities may occur where different data sources are combined (e. g., Maahn et al., 2015). For ground-based observations, this means that observations with high resolution instruments such as the MASC (Multi-Angle Snowfall Camera, Garrett et al., 2012) with a resolution of $30\ \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$, the sampling volume is not sufficient to provide reliable size distributions (Gergely and Garrett, 2016). Instead, the ground-based PIP (Precipitation Imaging Package, Pettersen et al., 2020) can provide robust size distributions, but the pixel resolution of $100\ \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$ is not sufficient enough for sharp particle images.

For particle size distributions, the maximum extension of the particles (D_{max}) or the area equivalent diameter (D_{eq}) are commonly used to characterize particle size. However, these parameters depend on the particle orientation, which cannot be controlled during the observations. Due to the fast platform movement, aircraft in situ sensors can observe particles from above. Assuming that particles precipitate with the major axis oriented horizontally, they can observe the true maximum extent. For ground-based sensors, this is not possible, because snow would accumulate on the instrument. Instead, observations can be made from multiple perspectives to minimize the error (e. g., Lawson et al., 2006; Garrett et al., 2012), but uncertainties remain (Jiang et al., 2017). Further, there are different definitions of D_{max} and aspect ratio (AR), which can lead to discrepancies (Wu and McFarquhar, 2016). For some instruments, the exact method of sizing the particle is unknown due to proprietary code and lack of documentation (Helms et al., 2022).

1.5 Inverse retrievals*

Typically, instruments measure a change in voltage, the number of photons entering a detector in a given time, a Doppler shift in radar frequency, and the intensity of backscattered energy. However, specific atmospheric variables are of interest, such as IWC at a given altitude or within a given volume, the temperature and water vapor at specific altitudes, or the cloud droplet number concentration. Thus, we need to extract

*This section has been adapted from Paper II (Maahn et al., 2020)

specific information from the observations that is typically only partially related to the variable of interest - this is commonly done by a retrieval. This is particularly relevant for remote sensing instruments, but is also a limitation of in situ instruments, e. g., when D_{\max} of an ice particle is estimated from an optical instrument, where the observed particle size depends on the orientation of the particle to the instrument. Typically, we can compute the signal that we would observe with our instrument using a forward model. I. e., if we knew the *atmospheric state*, which includes all variables affecting the observed signal, we could reproduce the *measurement state*. These forward models are ideally based on physical principles, but they are often nonlinear, which makes them difficult or even impossible to invert analytically. Thus, the retrieval problem is essentially the development of an algorithm to invert the forward model (F) so that we can derive the desired atmospheric variable (\mathbf{x} ; e. g., humidity, IWC , D_{\max}) from the observation (\mathbf{y} ; e. g., brightness temperature, Z_e , particle size at random orientation).

Typically, there are more unknowns than there are measurements so that there is no guarantee that there is only a unique \mathbf{x} that maps to the observation \mathbf{y} . It is possible that $F(\mathbf{x}) = F(\mathbf{x}') = \mathbf{y}$, where $\mathbf{x} \neq \mathbf{x}'$, which means that there are several different states mapping onto \mathbf{y} . Consequently, inversion problems are often ill-posed. Also, the retrieval has to handle uncertainties related to the instrument and the forward operator. Thus, we have to invert a set of noisy observations using an imperfect forward model, where several different \mathbf{x} could reproduce \mathbf{y} . Often a prior knowledge (i. e., a climatology) of atmospheric observations is used along with a forward model to simulate the observations that would be associated with each \mathbf{x} . Using a prior constrains ill-posed problems where the most likely state is selected from the possible solutions based on prior information. The accuracy of a retrieval will depend strongly on the prior information, i. e., the prior dataset with mean \mathbf{x}_a and covariance matrix \mathbf{S}_a . However, the benefit of adding information from the prior to the retrieval comes at the cost that the retrieval may perform poorly when applied to unlikely extreme events.

FIGURE 1.3: Optimal Estimation principle: The ellipses show the (left) prior state and (right) measurement uncertainty. The iterative process starts with applying the forward operator F to the first guess (here $\mathbf{x}_0 = \mathbf{x}_a$). Based on the difference of $F(\mathbf{x}_a)$ to \mathbf{y}_{obs} (which is close to but not equal to an ideal measurement $\mathbf{y}_{\text{truth}}$ representing $\mathbf{x}_{\text{truth}}$), \mathbf{x}_1 is obtained (which requires inverting F). This is repeated until the retrieval converges to a solution $\mathbf{x}_3 = \mathbf{x}_{\text{op}}$ that is close to the true state $\mathbf{x}_{\text{truth}}$. The blue contours describe the uncertainty of the solution \mathbf{x}_{op} . This Figure has been adapted from [Maahn et al. \(2020\)](#)

Many retrievals exploit the idea that the probability P of a certain atmospheric state \mathbf{x} given a measurement \mathbf{y} [$P(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{y})$] can be described by Bayes' theorem:

$$P(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{y}) = \frac{P(\mathbf{y}|\mathbf{x})P(\mathbf{x})}{P(\mathbf{y})}. \quad (1.4)$$

Bayes's theorem tells us that $P(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{y})$ can be obtained by multiplying the probability of \mathbf{y} given \mathbf{x} [$P(\mathbf{y}|\mathbf{x})$] representing the measurement uncertainty with the a priori probability density of the state $P(\mathbf{x})$ based on e. g., a climatology, a model forecast, or a measurement at some distance away in space or time. The division by $P(\mathbf{y})$ is effectively a normalization factor. The probability density function $P(\mathbf{x}|\mathbf{y})$ is already the solution for the inverse problem and includes an uncertainty estimate.

Optimal Estimation (OE, [Rodgers, 2000](#)) is a widely used physical retrieval method based on Bayes' theorem, assuming that all probabilities have a Gaussian distribution. OE attempts to find an optimal solution \mathbf{x}_{op} given an observation and prior information, i. e., \mathbf{x}_a and \mathbf{S}_a . The iteration is started with a first guess for the atmospheric state \mathbf{x}_0 , either from another instrument, model results, or \mathbf{x}_a . In the next step, the difference between $F(\mathbf{x}_a)$ and \mathbf{y}_{obs} is used to make the next guess \mathbf{x}_1 considering the distance from \mathbf{x}_1 to \mathbf{x}_a weighted by \mathbf{S}_a and the effective measurement uncertainty covariance matrix \mathbf{S}_e consisting of the measurement uncertainty \mathbf{S}_y and the forward operator uncertainty \mathbf{S}'_b . Obtaining \mathbf{x}_1 from \mathbf{x}_a and \mathbf{y}_{obs} requires inverting F which is typically not possible analytically. Therefore, the Jacobian $\mathbf{K} = \partial\mathbf{y}/\partial\mathbf{x}$ is used to linearize and invert F , leading to the requirement that F be moderately linear, which is satisfied for most problems in atmospheric science due to the lack of discontinuities. Since \mathbf{K} is only an approximation for F around \mathbf{x}_0 , the \mathbf{x}_1 obtained by this process is typically not yet the solution, and the process must be repeated until \mathbf{x} converges to a stable, optimal solution \mathbf{x}_{op} . \mathbf{K} depends on the \mathbf{x} used to estimate the Jacobian, which means that \mathbf{K} must be recalculated for each iteration step. Mathematically (see [Rodgers, 2000](#), for a detailed introduction), the iterative process for iteration $i + 1$ can be summarized with

$$\mathbf{x}_{i+1} = \mathbf{x}_a + (\mathbf{S}_a^{-1} + \mathbf{K}_i^T \mathbf{S}_e^{-1} \mathbf{K}_i)^{-1} \mathbf{K}_i^T \mathbf{S}_e^{-1} [\mathbf{y} - F(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{b}) + \mathbf{K}_i(\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_a)]. \quad (1.5)$$

In fact, F depends not only on \mathbf{x}_i , but also on the parameter vector \mathbf{b} , which includes additional input variables for the forward operator that are not retrieved by the algorithm and are considered fixed. The uncertainty of \mathbf{x}_i can be easily calculated with

$$\mathbf{S}_i = (\mathbf{S}_a^{-1} + \mathbf{K}_i^T \mathbf{S}_e^{-1} \mathbf{K}_i)^{-1}. \quad (1.6)$$

which is an important advantage of OE and other physical retrieval methods compared to statistical retrievals (e. g., [Cadeddu et al., 2009](#)). The iteration stops at iteration i if the change in \mathbf{x} is less than the derived uncertainty \mathbf{S}_i .

$$(\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_{i+1})^T \mathbf{S}_i^{-1} (\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_{i+1}) \ll \text{length}(\mathbf{x}). \quad (1.7)$$

OE is a powerful tool for retrieval development, but it is crucial to carefully estimate the prior (\mathbf{x}_a , \mathbf{S}_a) and the associated measurement and forward model errors (\mathbf{S}_e) in advance to avoid retrieval errors. Also, the fundamental requirements for OE applications must be fulfilled, i. e., the uncertainties must follow normal distributions in order to be quantified by covariance matrices and the forward operator must behave moderately linear.

1.6 Outline

This thesis addresses the long-standing problem of our insufficient observational capabilities leading to an incomplete process understanding of processes related to clouds and precipitation in Arctic regions. It consists of ten papers published in renown journals* organized around three key topics that define my main focus since receiving the title of Doctor rerum naturalium in 2015.

In the first topic *Improving measurements of clouds and precipitation*, I will present several studies enhancing our observational capabilities in various ways. For the second topic *Observing aerosol-cloud interaction* and third topic *Understanding the riming process*, the focus is on using advanced observations to study two specific cloud processes in the Arctic that are among the least understood processes. Concluding remarks are given in an outlook in [Chapter 5](#). Full copies of the ten papers can be found at the end of the thesis.

*One of the papers is currently in review

Chapter 2

Improving measurements of clouds and precipitation

Numerous observations of the Earth-atmosphere system are based on remote sensors (e. g., satellite observations, weather radar observations) used in a variety of operational and research applications. For these sensors, the atmospheric variables of interest are never directly observed, but must be derived from the observations through an inversion algorithm (i. e., retrieval), which often requires the use of prior assumptions. This multi-step process of converting raw instrument observations into quality-controlled atmospheric quantities is affected by uncertainties at all stages of the process chain. Artifacts in the observations and inaccurate calibrations can lead to incorrect atmospheric values. Inappropriate assumptions about the uncertainties in the observations, the forward operators, or the prior information can degrade the quality of the retrieval results. In the following, I present several studies that address these issues from different perspectives.

2.1 Using microphysical cloud processes for radar calibration*

When applying retrievals to radar observations, or comparing radar observations from different locations, accurate calibration is key. However, accurate radar calibration of ground-based radars is difficult (Atlas, 2002), and most approaches have relied either on calibration of all components separately in a laboratory (e. g., Chandrasekar et al., 2015) or on comparison with independent measurements from other sensors e. g., during precipitation (e. g., Frech et al., 2017). In Paper I (Maahn et al., 2019), we addressed this limitation by investigating whether observations of microphysical processes in liquid water clouds, such as the transition of cloud droplets to drizzle drops, can be used to calibrate vertically pointing cloud radars. To this end, we studied the relationship between the radar reflectivity factor Z_e and three variables not affected by absolute radar calibration: the skewness of the radar Doppler spectrum (γ), the radar mean Doppler velocity (W), and the liquid water path (LWP) observed by a collocated microwave radiometer (MWR).

For γ and W , we used the onset of drizzle for calibration by exploiting the unique relationships between γ , W , and Z_e for radar calibration. While W monotonically increases[†] during drizzle onset, γ shows a more complex behavior (e. g., Luke and Kollias, 2013). It is close to zero for liquid water clouds without drizzle due to the Gaussian shape of the radar Doppler spectrum, then positive when drizzle forms but the spectrum is still dominated by cloud droplets, before finally becoming negative

*This section summarizes Paper I (Maahn et al., 2019), individual parts were directly copied from the source.

[†]In this thesis, positive Doppler velocities refer to motion towards the radar

FIGURE 2.1: (a) reflectivity (Z_e) - skewness (γ) and (b) Z_e - mean Doppler-velocity (W) relationships for the individual model runs using synthetic initial model conditions. The black lines denote the medians as a function of Z_e , the error bars are estimated using bootstrapping for selected γ and W values. Color is for model run time. This figure has been adapted from Paper I (Maahn et al., 2019).

when the spectrum is dominated by drizzle droplets. The exact transition depends mainly on the initial cloud droplet size distribution. Therefore we used a box model (Hoffmann et al., 2017) to simulate drizzle onset and to identify the moment of drizzle onset that is suite dbest for radar calibration, i. e., with the lowest Z_e variability (Figure 2.1). Obviously, both γ and W are negatively affected by the presence of turbulence and/or vertical air motion, but we expect these to cancel out when the method is applied to longer time series.

Further, we investigated the potential of MWR-measured LWP for Z_e calibration, since Luke and Kollias (2016) suggested that the relationship between LWP and maximum reflectivity in the column Z_e contains information that can be used for radar calibration. LWP and Z_e are correlated because larger LWP values allow drops to grow larger by condensation and increase the probability of drizzle formation, leading to higher Z_e values (Acquistapace et al., 2019). But unlike the γ and W -based methods, which focus on a specific moment during drizzle formation, the LWP method is affected by the full set of processes of droplet growth and drizzle formation, including multiple feedback processes between clouds and their environment. Therefore, a boxmodel is not suited and we must rely on observations to develop a reference relationship between Z_e and LWP .

We applied all three methods to vertically pointing Ka-band radar observations of Arctic low-level liquid water clouds at the Atmospheric Radiation Measurement (ARM) user facility North Slope of Alaska (NSA) and Oliktok Point (OLI) sites. We

used monthly intervals to detect rapid changes but obtaining a sufficient number of liquid water cloud observations (for 15 s temporal resolution, at least 1000 data points). For NSA, the observed Z_e - γ and Z_e - W relations are in general agreement with the box model simulations, and we use the difference between measured and modeled Z_e reference values to evaluate the calibration offset O , defined as $O = Z_e^{\text{truth}} - Z_e^{\text{measured}}$, on a monthly basis. Considering the 3 dB uncertainties of the γ - and W -based methods, the calibration at NSA is relatively stable and the calibration offset O is on average about 1 dB (Figure 2.2.a). The stable calibration of the NSA radar motivated us to use the LWP - Z_e relation at NSA as a reference for absolute calibration using the LWP method. The variability of the estimated O for the LWP -based method is smaller than for γ and W , indicating that the LWP -based method is more stable.

FIGURE 2.2: Calibration offsets O (a, b) and number of observations used (c, d) for the North Slope of Alaska NSA (a, c) and Oliktok Point OLI (b, d). For OLI, the dotted lines show the preliminary results without modifying the phase classification. This figure has been adapted from Paper I (Maahn et al., 2019).

For OLI, we found serious problems with maintaining accurate radar calibration. Most notably, we found that O dropped from 5 to 7 dB in June 2016 (Figure 2.2.b), which was likely related to a change in radar configuration, although the details cannot be reconstructed. We are not aware of any other configuration changes at either site. In addition, we observed a slowly decreasing and increasing trend of O in the spring and fall of 2016, respectively. Similar to NSA, the agreement between the liquid water cloud-based methods decreases in winter, suggesting that a sufficient number of liquid water cloud samples is required for the method to work

properly. Nevertheless, the $Z_e - \gamma$, $Z_e - W$, and $LWP - Z_e$ relationships for OLI are consistent after applying a calibration correction, indicating the ability of the methods to correct for larger O values as long as the calibration offset is considered during phase classification (Shupe, 2007) for liquid water cloud identification. Due to the effect of turbulence on radar observations, the γ -based method is likely to work best for stratiform clouds, which are typically not as turbulent. Considering the error margins, our results are in excellent agreement with Kollias et al. (2019), who used the CloudSat-based method proposed by Protat et al. (2011) and found a similar decrease for OLI and a 3 dB offset for NSA. Compared to other calibration methods for cloud radars, the methods can be easily applied to past data sets and do not require an operational space-borne cloud radar as Protat et al. (2011). Furthermore, the method can be applied to year-round observations, even at high latitudes, since liquid water clouds are present throughout the year, although with limited accuracy in winter.

2.2 Optimal Estimation retrievals and their uncertainties*

After improving data quality in Paper I (Maahn et al., 2019), the quality of retrievals is discussed in Paper II (Maahn et al., 2020). For quantifying the uncertainty of retrieval results properly, it is important to quantify the uncertainties that arise from three sources: The prior data set used to either construct or constrain the retrieval (characterized by the covariance matrix \mathbf{S}_a), the uncertainties in the forward model assumptions and the ancillary input data sets used in the forward model (\mathbf{S}'_b), and the uncertainties in the observations themselves (\mathbf{S}_y). The latter two together form the effective measurement uncertainty (\mathbf{S}_e). Within the inversion algorithm, these uncertainties can be propagated to obtain uncertainties in the retrieved atmospheric state \mathbf{x}_{op} given by the covariance matrix \mathbf{S}_{op} . In a series of examples, we have used the Optimal Estimation (OE) retrieval method in Paper II (Maahn et al., 2020) to show the effects of how changes in these uncertainties lead to changes in \mathbf{x}_{op} and \mathbf{S}_{op} .

In Paper II (Maahn et al., 2020), we discuss how a non-Gaussian uncertainty distribution can lead to a degradation of OE performance. Instead, non-normally distributed state variables should be normalized to avoid negative effects on retrieval quality and robustness. Using forward operators that are grossly nonlinear (i. e., they cannot be correctly linearized using a Jacobian) will also lead to a decrease of accuracy. The impact of ignoring forward model error is illustrated in Figure 2.3 using a MWR temperature and humidity profile retrieval as an example. Ignoring the forward model error \mathbf{S}'_b (Cimini et al., 2018), the errors of the optimal solution \mathbf{S}_{op} are underestimated by up to 11 percentage points. The information content at the individual altitudes quantified by the degrees of freedom for signal, instead, is overestimated.

All examples can be run online in a web browser[†] which includes an open source Python library enabling readers to develop their own retrievals (pyOptimalEstimation, Maahn, 2020).

*This section summarizes Paper II (Maahn et al., 2020), individual parts were directly copied from the source.

[†]https://github.com/maahn/pyOptimalEstimation_examples

FIGURE 2.3: (a) The ratio of the uncertainty in the optimal solution (i. e., the square root of the diagonal of \mathbf{S}_{op}) to the uncertainty in the prior (i. e., the square root of the diagonal of \mathbf{S}_a) and (b) individual degrees of freedom for signal. The statistics for temperature are in green and statistics for specific humidity are in red. The solid line is the reference run considering only observational errors (\mathbf{S}_y) and the dashed dotted line is for the configuration where the forward model uncertainty (\mathbf{S}'_b) is added. This figure has been adapted from Paper II (Maahn et al., 2020). ©2020 AMS.

2.3 Introducing the Video In Situ Snowfall Sensor (VISSS)*

After addressing radar calibration and the proper handling of retrieval uncertainties in the first two papers, Paper III (Maahn et al., 2024) introduced a novel in situ instrument, the Video In Situ Snowfall Sensor (VISSS), for quantifying snowfall particle size and shape distributions. Its development was initially motivated by the need for improved instrumentation to collect in situ data sets with the goal to develop radar-based snowfall retrievals (Maahn et al., 2015; Maahn and Löhnert, 2017). However, the instrument also proved to be extremely valuable for microphysical studies. The objective was to develop a sensor with an open and well-defined sample volume without sacrificing optical resolution. VISSS uses gray scale images of particles in free fall illuminated by a background light (Figure 2.4, Table 2.1). This setup is duplicated with overlapping samplings so that particles are simultaneously observed from two perspectives at a 90° angle. This robustly constrains the observation volume. In addition, having two perspectives of the same particle increases the likelihood that the observed maximum dimension (D_{max}) and aspect ratio are representative of the particle. While the VISSS does not achieve microscopic resolution, its pixel resolution of $43 \mu\text{m px}^{-1}$ to $59 \mu\text{m px}^{-1}$ (depending on VISSS generation) is sufficient to resolve small particle details (Figure 2.4), and the use of telecentric lenses eliminates size errors caused by the variable distance of snow particles from the cameras. The VISSS hardware plans (Maahn et al., 2023; Maahn and Wolter, 2024), data acquisition software (Maahn, 2023a), and data processing libraries (Maahn, 2023b) have been released under an open source license.

*This section summarizes Paper III (Maahn et al., 2024), individual parts were directly copied from the source.

FIGURE 2.4: a) Conceptual drawing of the VISSS (not to scale with enlarged observation volume). b) First generation VISSS deployed at Gothic, Colorado during the SAIL campaign (photo by Benn Schmatz). c) Randomly selected particles observed during MOSAiC on 15 November 2019 between 6:53 and 11:13 UTC. This figure has been adapted from [Paper III \(Maahn et al., 2024\)](#).

[Paper III \(Maahn et al., 2024\)](#) describes the instrument and its data processing in great detail. The initial analysis shows the potential of the instrument. The relatively large observation volume of the VISSS leads to robust statistics based on up to 10,000 individual particle observations per minute. The Hyytiälä data set from winter 2021/22 is used to compare the VISSS with colocated Precipitation Imaging Package (PIP, [Pettersen et al., 2020](#)) and Parsivel ([Löffler-Mang and Joss, 2000](#)) instruments ([Figure 2.5](#)). The comparison with Parsivel shows—given the known limitations of the Parsivel for observing snowfall ([Battaglia et al., 2010](#)) and small droplets ([Thurai et al., 2019](#))—excellent agreement for snow and rain cases. Compared to VISSS and PIP, particle concentrations decrease for $D < 0.6$ mm, which is likely related to limitations associated with the Parsivel pixel resolution of $125 \mu\text{m}$. The comparison of VISSS and PIP shows larger discrepancies, which also depend on the snow particle shape and

TABLE 2.1: Technical specifications of the three VISSS instruments. The table has been adapted from [Paper III \(Maahn et al., 2024\)](#).

	VISSS1	VISSS2	VISSS3
Pixel resolution [$\mu\text{m px}^{-1}$]	58.75	43.125	46.0
Obs. volume (w x d x h) [mm]	75.2 x 75.2 x 60.1	55.2 x 55.2 x 44.2	58.9 x 58.9 x 47.1
Used frame size [px]	1280 x 1024	1280 x 1024	1280 x 1024
Frame rate [Hz]	140	250	225 (270 planned)
Effective exposure time [μs]	60	60	60
Working distance [mm]	227 mm	600 mm	1300 mm
Camera	Teledyne Genie Nano M1280	Teledyne Genie Nano 5G M2050	Teledyne Genie Nano 5G M2050
Lens	Opto Engineering TC12080	Sill S5LPJ1235 (with modified working distance)	Sill S5LPJ1725 (with modified working distance)
Maker	University of Colorado Boulder 2019	University of Cologne 2021	Leipzig University 2023
Deployments	MOSAiC 2019/20; Hyytiälä, FI 2021/22; SAIL, USA 2022/23; Eriswil, CH 2023/24	Ny-Ålesund, NO since 2021	Hyytiälä, FI since 2023

may indicate problems with the PIP data processing, as discussed in [Paper III \(Maahn et al., 2024\)](#). For particles smaller than 0.3 mm (i. e., 5 pixel), the first generation VISSS pixel resolution of 0.06 mm is likely to introduce discretization errors, potentially leading to errors in the sizing of very small particles. We also analyzed the advantage of the VISSS due to the availability of a second camera. Depending on the particle type, the mean D_{\max} increases up to 16 % and the mean aspect ratio (AR) decreases by 12 %. For the analyzed case, the VISSS observes each particle on average 8.5 times, which can further improve estimates of particle properties due to the natural rotation of the particle during sedimentation. Compared to using only a single camera, this can increase the mean D_{\max} by up to 24 % and reduce AR by up to 31 %.

FIGURE 2.5: (a-c) Particle size distributions of VISSS, PIP, and Parsivel for three cases on 26 January 2022 integrated over 1 minute. D_{eq} is used as the size descriptor. (d) Same as (a-c), but showing the drop size distribution of a drizzle case on 16 October 2021. In addition, the VISSS drop size distribution is also shown using D_{\max} as the size descriptor. This figure has been adapted from [Paper III \(Maahn et al., 2024\)](#).

Chapter 3

Observing aerosol-cloud interaction

Compared* to other regions, there are few sources of local anthropogenic emissions in the Arctic, mainly related to shipping and petroleum and natural gas extraction facilities (Law and Stohl, 2007). Ship emissions, which are expected to increase due to retreating sea ice (Peters et al., 2011), have been used as a natural laboratory (Possner et al., 2017; Gilgen et al., 2018) to study aerosol-cloud interaction (ACI), but are limited in extent and occurrence. In contrast to ship emissions, local emissions from Arctic oil and gas production facilities are typically continuous and spatially limited. Local emissions from this industry have been observed and quantified by aircraft campaigns in the Arctic (Brock et al., 2011; Roiger et al., 2015). These emissions are mostly associated with flaring, but also with regular combustion engines. Ødemark et al. (2012) found that black carbon (BC), produced primarily by flaring (Stohl et al., 2013), results in a local warming of the atmosphere, mainly due to deposition of BC on snow leading to surface albedo changes. Kolesar et al. (2017) showed that emissions from the Prudhoe Bay area lead to in situ particle growth events in Utqiagvik (formerly known as Barrow), located about 300 km west of the Prudhoe Bay region. Petroleum production in and around the Prudhoe Bay oil field has resulted in the continuous release of anthropogenic emissions over the past several decades, with annual anthropogenic sulfur dioxide emissions of 17.37 kt (Klimont et al., 2017). These rates are similar to those observed at mid-latitudes, although only a small area on the North Slope of Alaska is affected (Figure 3.1). Even though previous studies have demonstrated the potential impact of industrial activities in the Arctic (Hobbs and Rangno, 1998), in situ and remote sensing observations of clouds and aerosols have not been combined to investigate local sources of emissions.

In two papers, we extended the natural laboratory concept by investigating aerosol effects on clouds using in situ (Paper IV, Maahn et al., 2017) and satellite observations (Paper V, Maahn et al., 2021) from northern Alaska. In addition to localized aerosol sources, the North Slope of Alaska is characterized by flat terrain and limited spatial variability in meteorology: surface measurements of temperature, humidity, and surface pressure at Oliktok Point (OLI) and Utqiagvik (formerly Barrow) correlate 0.96, 0.95, and 0.97, respectively, according to data recorded at the ARM sites (Holdridge and Kyrouac, 1993). For Utqiagvik, Sedlar et al. (2021) found that cloud formation and dissipation are mostly controlled by synoptic drivers. This results in a favorable environment with limited confounding factors (Sena et al., 2016; Grandey and Wang, 2019) enabling to evaluate aerosol-cloud interactions in a natural, laboratory-like setting.

*This paragraph has been adapted from Maahn et al. (2017) and Maahn et al. (2021)

FIGURE 3.1: Annual sulfur dioxide emissions based on an inventory by Klimont et al. (2017) for the northern hemisphere and the study region (insert). The insert also shows isolines for elevation above sea level (gray) and a wind rose for the 925 hPa level at Oliktok Point based on ERA5. The green dots correspond to active oil wells in March 2017, and the green and orange boxes indicate the reference and Prudhoe Bay regions, respectively, used in Paper V (Maahn et al., 2021). This figure has been adapted from Paper V (Maahn et al., 2021).

3.1 In Situ analysis at the North Slope of Alaska*

In Paper IV (Maahn et al., 2017), we analyzed the airborne cloud properties and aerosol observations obtained during the 5th Airborne Carbon Measurements (ACME-V) campaign of the ARM program to study the influence of local pollution on Arctic liquid water clouds. The campaign took place in summer 2015 (Biraud, 2016; Biraud et al., 2016) and consisted of 38 research flights by the ARM Gulfstream G-159 (G-1) aircraft (Schmid et al., 2014, 2016). We compared liquid water cloud observations within 90 km of Oliktok Point (OLI) and Utqiagvik (for ARM's NSA site). These two sites provide an ideal opportunity to study the effects of local emissions on cloud properties: While OLI is surrounded by industrial activity related to oil and natural gas extraction (with most of them closer than 90 km), there are no significant local sources in the vicinity of NSA. In addition, we grouped observations closer than 90 km to the two more continental sites of Toolik and Ivotuk into a third dataset (labeled TOI). Flights influenced by forest fire emissions and long-range transport were manually excluded from the analysis by analyzing vertical profiles of Carbon monoxide and refractory black carbon (rBC) (Roiger et al., 2015; Creamean et al., 2018) supported by aerosol dispersion simulations performed with version 4 of the Hybrid Single Particle Lagrangian Integrated Trajectory (HYSPLIT) model (Stein et al., 2015). For the vertical profiles, the properties of the aerosol particles below and above the

*This section summarizes Paper IV (Maahn et al., 2017), individual parts were directly copied from the source.

clouds were grouped with the properties of the corresponding clouds. Consequently, a single below-cloud aerosol value is assigned to each data point within the same cloud, assuming that aerosol properties do not change at the scale of individual cloud profiles.

FIGURE 3.2: a) Mean r_e and b) mean standard deviation of r_e as a function of liquid water content (LWC). The green crosses indicate a significant difference between the regions around the Oliktok Point (OLI) and North Slope of Alaska (NSA) sites (5% confidence interval). This figure has been adapted from [Paper IV \(Maahn et al., 2017\)](#).

The analysis of the in situ observations shows that the mean effective radius (r_e) is reduced at OLI compared to NSA for the same liquid water content (LWC). This effect is most pronounced for $LWC > 0.1 \text{ g m}^{-3}$, while r_e values are more similar for $LWC < 0.1 \text{ g m}^{-3}$. Data obtained in a 90 km radius around the inland sites TOI for comparison show that the mean r_e values at the coastal site in OLI are closer to TOI (mean $7.2 \pm 3.1 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$) than to the second coastal site NSA. The decrease in r_e from NSA to OLI supports the hypothesis that CCN concentrations are elevated in the OLI region, since the first aerosol-cloud indirect effect implies that droplet size is reduced when more CCN is available (all else equal). [Figure 3.2.b](#) shows that not only the mean r_e is reduced at OLI, but also the width of the distribution as shown by the standard deviation. Further analysis in [Paper IV \(Maahn et al., 2017\)](#) shows that this leads to a reduction of collision coalescence and precipitation rates by up to two orders of magnitude around OLI, indicating a potential impact of local aerosol emissions on cloud lifetime.

Often, in situ aircraft cloud observations can be related to aerosol properties above and below the individual clouds. [Figure 3.3](#) relates in-cloud observations of LWC and r_e to below-cloud observations of rBC, similar to the approach of [Jackson et al. \(2012\)](#). It shows that the smallest r_e are associated with elevated rBC concentrations ($> 10 \text{ ng kg}^{-1}$) for both sites. Note that for both sites these high concentrations correspond to a single cloud. However, for OLI there are more elevated rBC concentrations ($> 4 \text{ ng kg}^{-1}$) for intermediate r_e values (5-10 μm). rBC can originate from biomass burning as well as anthropogenic sources, but the particle size is smaller for the latter ([Schwarz et al., 2008](#)), which is confirmed by the ACME-V rBC core size observations. Together with the elevated HYSPLIT concentrations analyzed in a companion paper ([Creamean et al., 2018](#)), this supports the idea that rBC measurements around OLI

FIGURE 3.3: liquid water effective radius r_e as a function of liquid water content LWC for NSA (Utqiagvik/Barrow) (a) and OLI (Oliktok Point) (b). Color indicates absolute values for refractory black carbon rBC concentration. This figure has been adapted from Paper IV (Maahn et al., 2017).

are associated with local emissions from Prudhoe Bay and not transported fire emissions. The coincidence of elevated rBC concentrations with reduced r_e for OLI, could indicate that the observed rBC acted as a CCN. However, this would require the rBC to be coated with more hygroscopic material (e. g., sulfate), since pure rBC does not serve as an efficient CCN (Weingartner et al., 1997). In summary, we found that ten of 24 clouds at OLI—but only one of 16 clouds at NSA—could be influenced by local anthropogenic emissions. Quantification of ACI (Equation 1.1, Feingold et al., 2001; McComiskey et al., 2009) is challenging due to the small data set. However, based on the assessment of clouds affected by both local emissions and forest fires, the results are consistent with previous studies of ACI in the Arctic environment (Zamora et al., 2016). Including previously excluded forest fire cases from the ACME-V campaign in the estimation of ACI does not significantly change the found relationship.

3.2 Remote sensing analysis at the North Slope of Alaska*

By design, in situ aircraft data like presented in Paper IV (Maahn et al., 2017) are focused on specific campaigns and cannot provide continuous observations. To properly assess the impact of local emissions on average cloud properties and the corresponding footprint, we analyzed nearly 14 years of MODIS (Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer) observations from the Terra and Aqua satellites. The MODIS products (MOD06L2, MYD06L2, collection 6, Platnick and Ackerman, 2015b,a) were nearest neighbor gridded at 2 km resolution, which greatly expands the dataset compared to published MODIS cloud products at daily resolution, as multiple daily passes are available at high latitudes. To quantify the effect of localized emissions, we selected a region of Prudhoe Bay for further analysis that includes almost all oil wells and is slightly extended downwind (see insert Figure 3.1, orange box) in accordance with the predominant wind direction from the east (see wind rose in Figure 3.1). To allow comparisons, we selected a reference region without oil wells

*This section summarizes Paper V (Maahn et al., 2021), individual parts were directly copied from the source.

between Utqiagvik and Prudhoe Bay with similar characteristics in terms of number of land pixels, proximity to the ocean, and elevation (see [Figure 3.1](#), green box).

In contrast to [Paper IV \(Maahn et al., 2017\)](#), which analyzed only liquid water clouds, we extended the analysis to liquid-containing clouds (i. e., liquid and mixed-phase clouds) as identified by the MODIS cloud phase flag. The study period was limited to April to September to minimize contamination related to known deficiencies in the retrieval algorithm for high solar zenith angles (SZA) ([Grosvenor and Wood, 2014](#); [Khanal et al., 2020](#)). Also, only single layer clouds with optical thickness greater than 5 were included ([Sourdeval et al., 2015](#); [Goren et al., 2018](#)). Pixels containing ocean or lakes were removed to ensure homogeneous surface properties. For snow-covered pixels according to [Ramsay \(1998\)](#); [Helfrich et al. \(2007\)](#); [U.S. National Ice Center \(2008\)](#), a retrieval developed for use over bright surfaces using the 1.6/2.1 μm channels [Platnick et al. \(2001\)](#) was used instead of the standard retrieval.

The data show how the mean effective cloud liquid water droplet radius (r_e) is reduced in the Prudhoe Bay region compared to the reference area. ([Figure 3.4.a](#)). The reduction of r_e is not homogeneous in the Prudhoe Bay region and is strongest in the eastern part (up to 1.0 μm). The area of reduced r_e extends about 100 km downwind in accordance with the prevailing easterly wind direction. This is consistent with the location of the largest sulfur dioxide emissions according to the inventory (insert [Figure 3.1](#)). Since the surface elevation in the area of reduced r_e is below 50 m (insert [Figure 3.1](#)), we assume that the effect of lifting processes on these signatures can be neglected. Characterizing the spatial variability of the r_e change, the 1st and 5th percentiles of the r_e values within the Prudhoe Bay region are reduced by 0.78 μm and 0.60 μm , respectively, but it should be noted that these values also depend on the boundaries used for the Prudhoe Bay region. The relatively small r_e reduction is explained by the fact that the data are temporally averaged over all cases and a variety of cloud types and background aerosol concentrations. For individual cases the r_e reduction can be as large as 10 μm ([Paper V, Maahn et al., 2021](#)).

To account for r_e variations in individual cases, we also compared the distributions of all MODIS cloud observations within the two regions, i. e., without temporal averaging (insert [Figure 3.4.a](#)). For the Prudhoe Bay region, we find that the median r_e is significantly (5% confidence interval, Mood's t-test) reduced by 0.28 μm compared to the reference region. Comparing the distributions of individual cases shows that the r_e reduction in the Prudhoe Bay region is stronger for the 75th percentile (0.44 μm difference between the two regions) than for the 25th percentile (0.21 μm difference). This shows the higher sensitivity of more pristine clouds with larger r_e values to changes associated with local pollution ([Platnick and Twomey, 1994](#)).

Restricting the analysis to times when winds were aligned with the prevailing wind direction (60° to 110° based on ECMWF 5th generation atmospheric reanalyses ERA5 at the 925 hPa level) the detected temporal mean r_e decrease becomes larger (up to 1.35 μm , [Figure 3.4.b](#)) and the median of the distribution of all cloud observations is reduced by 0.41 μm . Spatially, the plume extends more than 200 km to 153° W longitude, which corresponds to about 8 h of air mass lateral advection given the ERA5 mean 925 hPa wind speed of 7 m s^{-1} —consistent with the timescales reported by [Gryspeerd et al. \(2021\)](#) for ship tracks. The plume generally does not extend to Utqiagvik, although aerosol properties at Utqiagvik were found to be affected by local pollution 8% of the time [Kolesar et al. \(2017\)](#).

To further support the hypothesis that the observed changes in r_e are related to emissions from the Prudhoe Bay region, we use the MODIS cloud top pressure (CTP) retrieval to filter the dataset. This is done with the assumption that local emissions should affect lower clouds more directly than higher clouds, especially given the

FIGURE 3.4: (a) Spatial deviation of the mean MODIS liquid water cloud effective radius r_e compared to a reference region (green square). The MODIS standard retrieval is used during periods without snow on the ground, while the 1.6/2.1 μm retrieval is used during periods with snow cover. The normalized r_e distributions for all observations in the Prudhoe Bay region (orange quadrangle) and the reference region (green quadrangle) are shown in the inset, with the lines representing the median and the 25th and 75th percentiles. Gray circles indicate (from left to right) Utqiagvik, Oliktok Point, and Deadhorse; black lines indicate shorelines. (b) Same as (a), but restricted to the main wind direction, defined as 60° to 110° from ERA5 at 925 hPa at Oliktok Point. (c) Same as (a), but limited to clouds with MODIS cloud top pressure (CTP) greater than 750 hPa. The medians of the distributions of the two regions are significantly different (5% confidence interval) for all three data sets. This figure has been adapted from [Paper V \(Maahn et al., 2021\)](#).

stratified nature of the Arctic atmosphere. We assume that lower clouds, those with $CTP \geq 750$ hPa (Figure 3.4.c), also have lower cloud bases on average, making them more susceptible to local pollution effects. In fact, low clouds show more pronounced reductions in r_e around Prudhoe Bay (r_e reduction up to $1.13 \mu\text{m}$) than observed for the full data set (Figure 3.4.a).

We also examined cloud frequency of occurrence (CFO) and LWP , but pronounced regional gradients in CFO and LWP overlay possible local effects centered on the Prudhoe Bay area, prohibiting the identification of local effects. If there were such effects, they must be smaller than about 2 percentage points and 5 g m^{-2} for CFO and LWP , respectively. The change in upwelling solar radiation (ΔSW_{\uparrow}) is estimated from the difference in albedo $\Delta\alpha_C$ combined with the downwelling solar radiation at the surface (SW_{\downarrow}) and the corresponding CFO (Charlson et al., 1992; Meskhidze and Nenes, 2006). Our analysis showed that these anthropogenic aerosol effects on cloud properties are estimated to result in a mean increase in upwelling solar radiation (ΔSW_{\uparrow}) of up to 0.79 W m^{-2} for the period April to September.

Chapter 4

Understanding the riming process

Although riming is a key process for snowfall formation through efficient mass growth (Harimaya and Sato, 1989; Moisseev et al., 2017) and potentially secondary ice production (SIP) mechanisms (Hallett and Mossop, 1974), the process is difficult to quantify. In a series of papers led by collaborators and Ph.D. students, the observational capabilities of the riming process were improved. Paper VI (Vogl et al., 2022), reported how artificial neural networks can be used to retrieve riming from Doppler cloud radar observations. The methods for estimating the scattering properties of snow particles developed in Paper VII (Maherndl et al., 2023) laid the foundation for a riming retrieval combining in situ and remote sensing observations in Paper VIII (Maherndl et al., 2024a). This retrieval technique was applied to study the spatial variability of the riming process (Paper IV, Maherndl et al., 2024b). In Paper X (Luke et al., 2021), a method was developed to quantify SIP caused by rime splintering and freezing fragmentation.

4.1 Observing riming with cloud radar using artificial neural networks*

Common remote sensing retrievals of riming exploit the fact that riming increases the sedimentation velocity of snowfall, which can be observed with zenith pointing cloud radars (Mosimann, 1995; Kneifel and Moisseev, 2020) via the mean Doppler velocity (W). However, this approach fails in regions with complex orography or during convective events because the sedimentation velocity is no longer equal to W .

In Paper VI (Vogl et al., 2022), we investigated the ability of Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) to retrieve a Rime Mass Fraction index (FR_{ANN}) using ground-based, zenith-pointing cloud radar variables as input. Two ANN configurations were developed to investigate whether W could be omitted from a FR_{ANN} retrieval enabling to quantify FR_{ANN} independently of vertical air motion. ANN #1 is based on Z_e , W , the spectral edge width (i. e., the width from the left to the right edge of the spectrum above the noise floor; SEW), and skewness (γ) as input features. For ANN #2, W is omitted and only Z_e , SEW, and γ are used. Training data for the ANNs were acquired during the winter of 2014 in Finland (Petäjä et al., 2016), which includes colocated Ka-band cloud radar and in situ observations of snowfall with the Precipitation Imaging Package (PIP) (Pettersen et al., 2020). For the latter, riming was quantified using the approach of von Lerber et al. (2017).

The ANNs were additionally applied to several data sets from Chile and Germany, including a case recorded in Leipzig. To test the performance, the riming estimates

*This section summarizes Paper VI (Vogl et al., 2022), individual parts were directly copied from the source.

were evaluated by comparison with the method of von Lerber et al. (2017), triple-frequency radar observations (Kneifel et al., 2011, 2016), and VISSS observations (Maahn et al., 2024) (Figure 4.1). The latter comparison was only qualitative, as quantitative VISSS riming retrievals were not available at the time of the study.

FIGURE 4.1: Riming during the case on 19 March 2021 as predicted by (a) ANN 1 (SEW, Z_e , γ , and W) and (b) ANN 2 (SEW, Z_e , and γ). The images in panel (c) were taken by the VISSS during the period 14:40 to 14:50 UTC, the period 15:00 to 15:10 UTC, and the period 15:50 to 16:00 UTC, respectively. These periods are marked with pink lines on the time axis in panel (b). Pixels with an EDR above the threshold of $10^{-3} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-3}$ are shaded gray in panels (a) and (b). This figure has been adapted from Paper VI (Vogl et al., 2022).

The detailed analysis performed in Paper VI (Vogl et al., 2022) shows that ANNs can be successfully used for riming retrieval. The retrieval of FR_{ANN} by ANN #1 and ANN #2 is very similar, showing that the inclusion of W is not required, allowing the retrieval to be successfully applied in conditions with non-negligible vertical air motion. However, turbulent broadening of the radar Doppler spectrum was found to bias the ANNs for eddy dissipation rates greater than $10^{-3} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-3}$, so that the retrieval can only be applied in moderately convective conditions. This is caused by the strong influence of turbulence on SEW, which cannot be removed from the ANNs as it is essential for the retrieval quality.

While Paper VI (Vogl et al., 2022) was an important first step in the development of robust radar-based retrieval, the available training data set was rather limited. As extensive VISSS observations of riming are now available, this retrieval method can be further refined in the future.

4.2 A riming-dependent parameterization of scattering by snowflakes*

The retrieval developed in [Paper VI \(Vogl et al., 2022\)](#) for quantifying riming is based on a statistical approach. Although statistical retrievals are faster than physical retrievals, the latter have advantages in quantifying uncertainties and understanding retrieval quality (see also the discussion in [Paper II, Maahn et al., 2020](#)). However, a physical retrieval requires a forward operator (i. e., a radar simulator such as [Mech et al., 2020](#)) that can consistently account for riming when estimating the scattering properties of snow particles. Since this did not exist, the motivation of [Paper VII \(Maherndl et al., 2023\)](#) was to develop such a parameterization based on the Self-Similar Rayleigh-Gans Approximation (SSRGA, [Hogan and Westbrook, 2014](#)), paving the way for subsequent retrieval development.

In [Paper VII \(Maherndl et al., 2023\)](#), rimed ice crystal aggregates were simulated using an aggregation and riming model ([Leinonen et al., 2013](#); [Leinonen and Moisseev, 2015](#); [Leinonen and Szyrmer, 2015](#)). These synthetic ice particles ([Figure 4.2](#)) were used to develop a parameterization of the SSRGA parameters. Unlike [Paper VI \(Vogl et al., 2022\)](#), the normalized rime mass \mathcal{M} was used here, which is defined as

$$\mathcal{M} = \frac{m_{\text{rime}}}{m_{\text{g}}} \quad (4.1)$$

where m_{rime} is the rime mass and m_{g} is the mass of the size-equivalent spherical graupel particle. This quantitative riming measure is consistent with atmospheric models ([Seifert et al., 2019](#)) and \mathcal{M} is better suited to represent the continuous riming process ([Tridon et al., 2022](#)).

FIGURE 4.2: Growth of two example aggregates by riming when exposed to an effective liquid water path ($ELWP$) of 2.0 kg m^{-2} . Top: aggregate of 300 needles with average monomer crystal sizes of $200 \mu\text{m}$. Bottom: aggregate of 30 dendrites with average monomer crystal sizes of $100 \mu\text{m}$. The rimed aggregates consist of cubic volume elements $20 \mu\text{m}$ wide; the scale shown in the first panel is the same for images of each row. The normalized rime mass \mathcal{M} at the different levels is shown above each image. The larger needle aggregate does not reach higher \mathcal{M} values than 0.224 with the selected $ELWP$. This figure has been adapted from [Paper VII \(Maherndl et al., 2023\)](#).

The riming-dependent parameterization of the SSRGA parameters was compared to backscattering cross section estimated with DDA ([Tyynelä et al., 2013](#)), which is considered the "gold standard" for estimating single particle scattering properties, but computationally expensive. As shown in [Figure 4.3](#), the SSRGA-derived backscattering cross sections agree well with the DDA results for Ka-band (35 GHz) and W-band (94 GHz): the mean biases for particles in a given \mathcal{M} bin are in the range -1.11 dB to -0.37 dB and -0.54 dB to 1.57 dB for the Ka-band and W-band, respectively, for

*This section summarizes [Paper VII \(Maherndl et al., 2023\)](#), individual parts were directly copied from the source.

$D_{\max} < \lambda$. For larger particles, the bias can increase up to four orders of magnitude, especially for slightly rimed particles. However, this bias is reduced to max. 0.5 dB (1.2 dB) for Ka-band (W-band) when integrating over typical size spectra (not shown). A comparison of reflectivity estimates from the SSRGA riming-dependent parameterization with results for fixed SSRGA parameters as used in previous studies (Hogan and Westbrook, 2014; Westbrook and Sephton, 2017) shows that the riming-dependent parameterization avoids biases in the backscattering cross section of up to 8 dB (see Fig. 6 of Paper VII, Maherndl et al., 2023).

FIGURE 4.3: SSRGA and DDA backscattering cross sections for rimed aggregates of different sizes for (a) 35.6 GHz and (b) 94.0 GHz, note the different scales. The vertical gray dashed lines show the wavelength. Unrimed particles ($\mathcal{M} = 0$) are shown in gray. Individual markers represent the DDA, while the lines show the running average of the SSRGA results. The SSRGA calculations used the riming-dependent parameterization and the exact particle masses. This figure has been adapted from Paper VII (Maherndl et al., 2023).

The aggregation and riming model was also used to develop coefficients of the mass-size and area-size relations that vary with \mathcal{M} (Figure 4.4). Consistent with previous studies (Leinonen and Szyrmer, 2015), the results do not confirm the so-called fill-in model (Heymsfield, 1982), which hypothesizes constant exponents of the mass-size and area-size relations caused by the assumption that riming fills smaller particle gaps first without changing the maximum dimension of the particles. Establishing the connection between riming quantified with a physical definition and the mass-size relation is an important advance over previous studies using subjective riming criteria (Mitchell, 1996; Mason et al., 2018). Together with the derived riming-dependent SSRGA parameters, single particle backscattering properties can be continuously estimated as a function of \mathcal{M} , setting the stage for subsequent retrieval developments for riming.

4.3 Quantifying riming from airborne data during HALO-(AC)³*

In Paper VIII (Maherndl et al., 2024a), the riming parameterization of Paper VII (Maherndl et al., 2023) was used to develop a riming retrieval for data collected during the HALO-(AC)³ aircraft campaign (Wendisch et al., 2024). In this field study, the Polar 5 and Polar 6 aircraft collected spatially and temporally closely collocated

*This section summarizes Paper VIII (Maherndl et al., 2024a), individual parts were directly copied from the source.

FIGURE 4.4: Results of the fit parameters of the power-law (a) mass-size a_m , b_m and (b) area-size a_A , b_A relationship fits for the studied monomer crystal types and normalized rime mass \mathcal{M} values. The b parameters are plotted against the a parameters in SI units. The color represents the corresponding \mathcal{M} bin, results for unrimmed particles ($\mathcal{M} = 0$) are shown in gray. Monomer crystal types are distinguished by markers: columns correspond to triangles, dendrites to stars, needles to minus signs, plates to squares, and rosettes to plus signs. Mean values across all types for each \mathcal{M} bin are shown as circles. This figure has been adapted from Paper VII (Maherndl et al., 2023).

radar and in situ data west of Svalbard in spring 2022. The retrieval method is based on the Optimal Estimation method introduced in Paper II (Maahn et al., 2020) and estimates \mathcal{M} from a closure between radar and in situ measurements during colocated flights, hereafter referred to as "combined method". The \mathcal{M} is chosen such that the simulated radar reflectivities Z_e , obtained from the observed in situ PSD, match the observed Z_e values. To estimate Z_e based on the PSD and \mathcal{M} , the passive and active microwave radiative transfer tool (PAMTRA Mech et al., 2020) was used with the riming-dependent parameterization of Paper VII (Maherndl et al., 2023). For comparison, we also developed a method to derive \mathcal{M} from in situ measured particle shape alone ("in situ method"). For this, we computed the complexity χ relating particle perimeter p to area A :

$$\chi = \frac{p}{2\sqrt{\pi A}}. \quad (4.2)$$

Similar to the approach for the SSRGA coefficients presented in Paper VII (Maherndl et al., 2023), we have empirically derived a $\chi - \mathcal{M}$ relationship from synthetic particles so that \mathcal{M} can be estimated from the in situ observations.

Both methods were applied to the colocated flight segments of the HALO-(AC)³ campaign. Statistically, we observed good agreement between the two methods, with median values of \mathcal{M} for the combined and in situ methods being 0.024 and 0.021, respectively. For all colocated flight segments, we find average rimed fractions of 88 % and 87 %, respectively, assuming that particles with a \mathcal{M} values less than 0.01 are unrimed. When looking at individual data points, the differences between the two methods can be much larger. This is likely due to a number of effects. First, the assumption of the collocation criterion that conditions are sufficiently homogeneous on scales up to 5 km does not always hold. Second, the observation volumes of in situ and remote sensing instruments are very different (about 10 000 m³ and about 1 cm³, respectively). Third, the Z_e and hence the retrieved \mathcal{M} used by the combined method is dominated by larger particles, while the in situ method is mostly based on observations of medium-size particles.

FIGURE 4.5: Occurrence of riming during colocated flight segments derived by combined (black) and in situ (magenta) methods as a function of (a)-(d) Polar 6 noseboom temperature in $^{\circ}\text{C}$, (e)-(h) Nevzorov probe measured LWC in g m^{-3} , (i)-(l) Nevzorov probe measured TWC in g m^{-3} , (m)-(p) MiRAC-A retrieved LWP in g m^{-2} , and (q)-(t) normalized measurement height in the cloud (0 means bottom of cloud, 1 means top of cloud). Bin sizes are 2°C , 0.02 g m^{-3} (0.005 g m^{-3} below 0.02 g m^{-3}), 0.025 g m^{-3} , 20 g m^{-2} , and 0.05 respectively. The first column shows the number of data points per bin. The second column shows the rimed fraction, assuming $\mathcal{M} < 0.01$ to be unrimed, derived by the combined (black squares) and in situ (magenta circles) methods. Uncertainty estimates are shaded (combined: OE standard deviation, in situ: 30 s running standard deviation). The third and fourth columns show 2D histograms of \mathcal{M} results for the combined and in situ methods, respectively, with medians for each bin in white. The black dashed line indicates $\mathcal{M} = 0.01$. All values with $\mathcal{M} < 0.01$ are grouped in the lowest bin. Medians and average rimed fractions are shown only, when there are more than 100 data points per bin. Nevzorov probe data are only available in April. This figure has been adapted from [Paper VIII \(Maherndl et al., 2024a\)](#).

Using both methods, we examined how \mathcal{M} depends on air temperature, LWC , LWP , and the normalized measurement location within the cloud (Figure 4.5). When comparing the two methods with respect to the normalized position within the cloud, we find that the differences are largest at the top of the cloud, where we expect the highest spatial variability, and at the bottom of the cloud, where only the combined method, but not the in situ method, is likely affected by larger precipitation particles due to poor sampling. With both methods, we do not find a clear relationship between LWC and riming during the colocated segments. However, this is likely due to the fact that rimed particles are typically rimed at different locations in the cloud than where they are observed. LWP shows a positive correlation with riming except for LWP values above 130 g m^{-2} where observations were sparse. When comparing \mathcal{M} with ambient temperature, a minimum of \mathcal{M} is found at about -15°C , corresponding to the dendritic growth zone (Takahashi et al., 1991; Takahashi, 2014). These results hold when applying the in situ technique to all Polar 6 flights, provided that low flight periods are not included.

4.4 The influence of riming on the spatial variability of mixed-phase clouds*

In Paper IV (Maherndl et al., 2024b), we used the scattering parameterization of Paper VII (Maherndl et al., 2023) and the retrievals developed in Paper VIII (Maherndl et al., 2024a) to investigate how riming affects snowfall formation by comparing the spatial variability of the riming process to IWC . In addition to the HALO-(\mathcal{AC})³ observations, we used data from the IMPACTS (Investigation of Microphysics and Precipitation for Atlantic Coast-Threatening Snowstorms, McMurdie et al., 2022) campaign. For both campaigns, tightly colocated cloud radar and in situ observations are available allowing to apply the combined method of Paper VII (Maherndl et al., 2023). Pair correlation functions (PCF) are used to quantify the dominant spatial scales of the IWC . The cluster probability η describes the homogeneity of the observed clouds. For this, a Monte-Carlo random test is performed for specific sampling distances according to Deng et al. (2024). For each flight segment, a random sub-segment of different track distances (from 1 km to 15 km in 1 km steps) is selected. The parameter (η) is calculated for each track distance for different lags to identify the scales at which clustering occurs. Figure 4.6 shows η for the number of ice particles N_i , the ice water content considering riming IWC_r , and the ice water content calculated using a mass-size relation assuming unrimed particles IWC_u . The comparison of IWC_r and IWC_u therefore shows the effect of riming on IWC and consequently ice formation. For IMPACTS, it is found that riming increases the variability of IWC , but does not change the associated scales (Figure 4.6.d). For HALO-(\mathcal{AC})³ (Figure 4.6.h), variability is enhanced not only on scales consistent with the roll cloud structure of cloud air outbreaks below 2 km, but also on spatial scales of 3 km to 5 km. Because increased cloud top height variability was also found at the same scales, we concluded that this increased variability is most likely related to the presence of mesoscale updrafts. These updrafts cause small particles to be lifted, increasing the cloud top height. Also, due to the increased vertical motion, ice particles are suspended longer, have more time to rime, and can reach higher masses (i. e., higher IWC_r) before precipitating. Increased LWP may increase the amount of riming, but is not a necessary criterion based on the cases analyzed. This hypothesis is supported by

*This section summarizes Paper IV (Maherndl et al., 2024b), individual parts were directly copied from the source.

theoretical analysis presented in Paper IV (Maherndl et al., 2024b) following Fitch and Garrett (2022) showing that the observed LWP is not sufficient to explain the retrieved rime masses and updrafts are required.

FIGURE 4.6: Average pair correlation function (PCF) η as a function of distance and lag calculated using all (a-c) IMPACTS and (e-g) HALO-(AC)³ flight segments for (a)&(e) N_i , (b)&(f) ice water content (IWC) accounting for riming IWC_r , and (c)&(g) IWC assuming no riming IWC_u . The difference between (b) and (c) is shown in (d); difference between (f) and (g) in (h). Differences in (d) and (h) are only shown when larger than 0. Areas where differences are significant according to a Student's t-test (95% significance threshold) are hatched. $\eta = 0$ is drawn as shaded lines for the ice number concentration N_i (dash-dotted black), IWC_r (solid black), IWC_u (dashed black), and liquid water content (LWC , solid blue), where LWC measurements from King probe (Nevzorov probe) measurements obtained during IMPACTS (HALO-(AC)³) are used. This figure has been adapted from Paper IV (Maherndl et al., 2024b).

4.5 Observing secondary ice production with cloud radar*

In Paper X (Luke et al., 2021), the relation of the riming process to SIP by rime splintering and freezing fragmentation is investigated. Rime splintering as proposed by Hallett and Mossop (1974) is often considered to be the most important SIP mechanism along with freezing fragmentation (Lauber et al., 2018). Previous studies were mostly based on laboratory experiments and it is unclear whether their results can be directly transferred to atmospheric applications. Six years of cloud radar observations from the NSA ARM site (Verlinde et al., 2016) were analyzed. Using the Doppler spectral information of Z_e and linear depolarization ratio (LDR), radar Doppler spectra were identified that contained rimed particles, drizzle, and high concentrations of small ice particles assumed to be formed by SIP. The frequency of occurrence of the SIP class ranges from 1% to 10% with a maximum at about -4.5°C , consistent with rime splintering (Hallett and Mossop, 1974). The dataset also allows distinguishing between the rime splintering and freezing fragmentation processes

*This section summarizes Paper X (Luke et al., 2021), individual parts were directly copied from the source.

FIGURE 4.7: Population of range gates containing cloud droplets (black dots; top axis) binned into 1°C intervals, and fraction of secondary ice events relative to the number of range gates containing cloud droplets (red dots; bottom axis) binned into 10 subsets of equal population. A-D show four subclasses: (A) neighborhoods with no rimed particles or drizzle, (B) those with only rimed particles, (C) those with only drizzle, and (D) those with both rimed particles and drizzle. The red dots represent the fraction of secondary ice events, while the gray shading represents an uncertainty estimate. This figures has been adapted from [Paper X](#) (Luke et al., 2021).

by relating the identified SIP Doppler spectra to Doppler spectra containing rime or drizzle in close proximity. This analysis shows that the class without rimed particles or drizzle (i. e., the background class) occurs most frequently. For this category, up to 4% of the observations contain particles stemming from SIP (Figure 4.7.a). When analyzing cases where rimed particles are present, the percentage of cases including particles from SIP does not increase, indicating that rime splintering is in nature not an efficient SIP (Figure 4.7.b). Instead, when drizzle is present, the fraction of secondary ice events is two to three times greater, suggesting that drizzle is a more important factor in SIP than rimed particles. The maximum occurs at a temperature

of about -4°C , but this could also be related to the fact that our method requires the presence of needles, which grow best at these temperatures, regardless of whether SIP occurs or not. When both rimed particles and drizzle are present, the highest proportion of secondary ice was observed at temperatures between -4°C and -6°C . Further analysis revealed that the rimed particles' velocity affects the SIP in cases where rimed particles and drizzle are colocated. For drizzle, however, it is found that the drop size correlates with an increase in the occurrence of SIP. This suggests that freezing fragmentation is more efficient for SIP than rime splintering in slightly supercooled clouds.

Chapter 5

Outlook

Although significant progress has been made in understanding the Arctic climate system, there are still many opportunities for further research. The studies presented in the first topic *Improving measurements of clouds and precipitation* contribute to the improvement of our observational capabilities, which is key to a better understanding of cloud and precipitation processes. But there are probably endless possibilities for further improvements. The applicability of the radar calibration technique developed in [Paper I \(Maahn et al., 2019\)](#) to regions other than the North Slope of Alaska should be explored. The effect of errors on the inverse Optimal Estimation retrieval has been extensively discussed in [Paper II \(Maahn et al., 2020\)](#), but additional work is needed to understand the limitations of the Optimal Estimation method with respect to nonlinear forward operators or non-Gaussian distributed variables. The development of VISSS presented in [Paper III \(Maahn et al., 2024\)](#) was mainly motivated by the lack of high quality in situ observations of snowfall needed to develop the a priori of radar-based snowfall retrievals. Now that three VISSS instruments have been successfully deployed in different regions of the world for a total of nine winters, this data is finally available and the retrieval concepts developed in my PhD thesis can be revisited ([Maahn et al., 2015](#); [Maahn and Löhnert, 2017](#)). Beyond retrieval development, VISSS can provide valuable insights into snowfall formation processes through the observed fingerprints of processes on snow particles. This will allow new insights into processes such as aggregation, riming, and sublimation; studies targeting microphysical processes with the VISSS have already begun. Finally, the potential of the VISSS for monitoring flying insects will be assessed, given the technical challenges of monitoring insect populations in the face of observed insect declines.

For the second topic *Observing aerosol-cloud interaction*, observations are used to understand the aerosol-cloud interaction process. The series of papers clearly shows the influence of local oil production facilities on cloud properties on the North Slope of Alaska. Since [Paper IV \(Maahn et al., 2017\)](#) only cover data from a single summer aircraft campaign, and the MODIS retrievals used in [Paper V \(Maahn et al., 2021\)](#) require daylight, the question of how cloud properties change during polar night—where they potentially have a greater impact on the radiative budget—remains open. I spent a lot of time comparing ground-based remote sensing observations of the ARM sites on the North Slope of Alaska and at Oliktok Point, but I was not able to detect any effect of local pollution on the observations at Oliktok Point. The reason is probably that advection of emissions from the Prudhoe Bay oil field toward Oliktok Point would require wind from the south, which is rare. I still think that the local emissions in an otherwise pristine region provide an excellent opportunity to study aerosol-cloud interactions, but we will probably have to wait for the availability of better data to study this topic further.

Riming and secondary ice formation are key processes in snowfall formation. The toolkit developed in the third topic *Understanding the riming process* opens new

ways to evaluate atmospheric models. The scattering parameterization of [Paper VII \(Maherndl et al., 2023\)](#) will allow better forward model simulations of atmospheric models with microphysical schemes that include riming quantities as a prognostic variable. However, future studies should investigate the quality of the simulated ice particles of the aggregation and riming model, e. g., by comparison with VISSS. The riming retrievals of [Paper VIII \(Maherndl et al., 2024a\)](#) can also be applied to ground-based in situ data such as VISSS, allowing to greatly expand the available data set and to quantify the contribution of the riming process to total snowfall. In a second step, these riming observations can be used to calibrate the radar-based riming retrieval presented in [Paper VI \(Vogl et al., 2022\)](#), so that vertical profiles of normalized rime mass (\mathcal{M}) could be retrieved. Using the methods for separating the effect of riming on *IWC* from other growth processes ([Paper IV, Maherndl et al., 2024b](#)), we can overcome the limitations of comparing simplistic *IWC* histograms between models and observations. Instead, a future study could evaluate whether a model can reproduce the riming process at the correct spatial scales. The SIP retrieval of [Paper X \(Luke et al., 2021\)](#) emphasized the relative importance of freezing fragmentation as opposed to rime splintering, but additional studies are desirable to investigate whether this holds for other locations and when applying less stringent filtering to the dataset.

The Arctic is a fascinating, beautiful region and there is no shortage of open research questions, also beyond the scope of this thesis. I hope that this unique part of the world can be preserved so that future generations of scientists can enjoy its beauty and advance our knowledge of the uniqueness of the Arctic climate system.

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Appendix

A Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
2DS	2 Dimensional Stereo optical array probe
(AC) ³	Arctic Amplification: Climate Relevant Atmospheric and Surface Processes, and Feedback Mechanisms
ACI	Aerosol Cloud Interaction
ACME-V	5th ARM Airborne Carbon Measurements
ANN	Artificial Neural Networks
ARM	Atmospheric Radiation Measurement user facility
BC	Black Carbon
CCN	Cloud Condensation Nuclei
CDP	Cloud Droplet Probe
DDA	Discrete Dipole Approximation
ERA5	5th generation ECMWF atmospheric reanalysis
HALO	High Altitude and Long range aircraft
HVPS	High Volume Precipitation Spectrometer
HYSPLIT	Hybrid Single Particle Lagrangian Integrated Trajectory
IMPACTS	Investigation of Microphysics and Precipitation for Atlantic Coast-Threatening Snowstorms
INP	Ice Nucleating Particles
MASC	Multi-Angle Snowfall Camera
MODIS	Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer
MOSAiC	Multidisciplinary drifting Observatory for the Study of Arctic Climate
MWR	MicroWave Radiometer
NSA	North Slope of Alaska site
OE	Optimal Estimation
OLI	Oliktok Point site
PAMTRA	Passive and Active Microwave radiative TRANSfer
PCF	Pair correlation function
PIP	Precipitation Imaging Package
PSD	Particle Size Distribution
RADAR	RADio Detection and Ranging
rBC	refractory Black Carbon
SAIL	Surface Atmosphere Integrated Field Laboratory
SIP	Secondary Ice Production
SR	Snowfall Rate
SSRGA	Self-Similar Rayleigh Gans Approximation
SZA	Solar Zenith Angle
TOI	Toolik & Ivotuk sites
VISS	Video In Situ Snowfall Sensor

B List of Symbols

Symbol	Name	Unit
a_A	Prefactor area-size relation	
a_m	Prefactor mass-size relation	
A	Area	m^2
AR	Aspect Ratio	
b_A	Exponent Area-size relation	
b_m	Exponent mass-size relation	
b	Parameter vector	
CFO	Cloud Frequency of Occurrence	
CTP	Cloud Top Pressure	hPa
D_{max}	Particle maximum dimension	m
D_{eq}	Particle area equivalent size	m
D	Particle size	m
$ELWP$	Effective Liquid Water Path	$kg\ m^{-2}$
F	Forward operator	
FR	Rime Mass Fraction	
i	Iteration index	
IWC	Ice Water Content	$kg\ m^{-3}$
K	Jacobian matrix	
K_w	Dielectric constant for water	
LDR	Linear Depolarization Ratio	dB
LWC	Liquid Water Content	$kg\ m^{-3}$
LWP	Liquid Water Path	$kg\ m^{-2}$
m_g	Mass of size-equivalent spherical graupel particle	kg
m_{rime}	Rime Mass	kg
\mathcal{M}	Normalized rime mass	
N_a	Number concentration of aerosols	m^{-3}
N_i	Number concentration of ice particles	m^{-3}
N_{tot}	Number concentration of cloud droplets	m^{-3}
N	Particle number distribution	$m^{-3}\ m^{-1}$
O	Calibration offset	dB
P	Probability density function	
p	Perimeter	m
r_e	Cloud droplet effective radius	m
\mathbf{S}_a	Covariance matrix a priori	
\mathbf{S}'_b	Covariance matrix forward operator uncertainty	
\mathbf{S}_e	Covariance matrix effective measurement uncertainty	
\mathbf{S}_{op}	Covariance matrix optimal solution for \mathbf{x}	
\mathbf{S}_y	Covariance matrix measurement uncertainty	
\mathbf{S}	Retrieved uncertainty of \mathbf{x}	
SW_{\downarrow}	Downwelling solar radiation	$W\ m^{-2}$
SW_{\uparrow}	Upwelling solar radiation	$W\ m^{-2}$
SEW	Spectral Edge Width of the Doppler spectrum	$m\ s^{-1}$
W	mean Doppler velocity	$m\ s^{-1}$
\mathbf{x}_a	Mean a priori for \mathbf{x}	
\mathbf{x}_{op}	Optimal solution for \mathbf{x}	
\mathbf{x}_{truth}	True atmospheric state	

Symbol	Name	Unit
\mathbf{x}	Atmospheric state vector	
\mathbf{y}_{obs}	Measured observation vector	
$\mathbf{y}_{\text{truth}}$	Ideal measurement representing $\mathbf{x}_{\text{truth}}$	
\mathbf{y}	Observation state vector	
Z_e	Equivalent Radar Reflectivity Factor	dBz*
α_C	Cloud albedo	
γ	Doppler spectrum skewness	
η	Cluster probability	
$\tilde{\eta}$	Radar reflectivity	$\text{m}^2 \text{m}^{-3}$
λ	Wavelength	mm
σ_b	Backscattering cross section	m^2
χ	Particle complexity	

*I prefer dBz to dBZ following [Smith \(2010\)](#)

Declaration of Authorship

I hereby declare that the present thesis has been produced by myself and without the assistance of further individuals or parties. All used sources have been included in the list of references. Reproduced or adapted text passages, tables and figures have been marked as such or provided with the respective reference. All papers included in this thesis have been reprinted with the permission of the respective publishers.

I also confirm that this thesis or a similar version of this thesis has neither been submitted nor rated elsewhere to achieve the academic degree of Doctor rerum naturalium habilitatus. The electronic version of this thesis is identical to the printed version which has been submitted to the habilitation commission at the Faculty of Physics and Earth System Sciences at Leipzig University.

Leipzig, 16 June 2025

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 2024 – 2027 DFG CRC-172 (*AC*)³ project *E05 Process-level Understanding of Sublimation and Evaporation of Precipitation* (336 k€)
 2023 - 2026 DFG project *EMPOS Evaluating Microphysical Pathways Of Midlatitude Snow Formation* (256 k€)
 2023 – 2024 Saxon State Ministry for Science, Culture and Tourism. Strengthening the competitiveness of a Cluster of Excellence *Breathing Nature* for the next phase of the Excellence Strategy (82 k€)
 2022 – 2025 DFG SPP PROM project *CORSIPP Characterization of orography-influenced riming and secondary ice production and their effects on precipitation rates using radar polarimetry and Doppler spectra* (349 k€)
 2021 – 2023 DFG CRC-172 (*AC*)³ project *B08 Characterising the spatial variability of ice water content in and below mixed-phase clouds* (166 k€)
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Peer Reviewed Publications

1. Wendisch, M., Crewell, S., Ehrlich, A., Herber, A., Kirbus, B., Lüpkes, C., Mech, M., Abel, S. J., Akansu, E. F., Ament, F., Aubry, C., Becker, S., Borrmann, S., Bozem, H., Brückner, M., Clemen, H.-C., Dahlke, S., Dekoutsidis, G., Delanoë, J., De La Torre Castro, E., Dorff, H., Dupuy, R., Eppers, O., Ewald, F., George, G., Gorodetskaya, I. V., Grawe, S., Groß, S., Hartmann, J., Henning, S., Hirsch, L., Jäkel, E., Joppe, P., Jourdan, O., Jurányi, Z., Karalis, M., Kellermann, M., Klingebiel, M., Lonardi, M., Lucke, J., Luebke, A. E., Maahn, M., Maherndl, N., Maturilli, M., Mayer, B., Mayer, J., Mertes, S., Michaelis, J., Michalkov, M., Mioche, G., Moser, M., Müller, H., Neggers, R., Ori, D., Paul, D., Paulus, F. M., Pilz, C., Pithan, F., Pöhlker, M., Pörtge, V., Ringel, M., Risse, N., Roberts, G. C., Rosenburg, S., Röttenbacher, J., Rückert, J., Schäfer, M., Schaefer, J., Schemann, V., Schirmacher, I., Schmidt, J., Schmidt, S., Schneider, J., Schnitt, S., Schwarz, A., Siebert, H., Sodemann, H., Sperzel, T., Spreen, G., Stevens, B., Stratmann, F., Svensson, G., Tatzelt, C., Tuch, T., Vihma, T., Voigt, C., Volkmer, L., Walbröl, A., Weber, A., Wehner, B., Wetzell, B., Wirth, M., and Zinner, T.: Overview: Quasi-Lagrangian Observations of Arctic Air Mass Transformations – Introduction and Initial Results of the HALO-(AC)³ Aircraft Campaign, *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 24, 8865–8892, doi:[10.5194/acp-24-8865-2024](https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-24-8865-2024), 2024
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Data sets and code publications (first author only)

1. Maahn, M., and N. Maherndl (2024), Video In Situ Snowfall Sensor (VISSS) data for Ny-Ålesund (July 2022 - December 2023), doi:[10.1594/PANGAEA.965766](https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.965766)
2. Maahn, M., and S. Wolter (2024), Hardware design of the Video In Situ Snowfall Sensor v3 (VISSS3), doi:[10.5281/zenodo.10526898](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10526898)
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4. Maahn, M., R. Haseneder-Lind, and P. Krobot (2023), Hardware design of the Video In Situ Snowfall Sensor v2 (VISSS2), doi:[10.5281/zenodo.7640821](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7640821)
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8. Maahn, M. (2023), Maahn/VISSSlib: V2023.1.6, Zenodo, doi:[10.5281/zenodo.7773717](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7773717)
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11. Maahn, M. (2020), "pyOptimalEstimation" Package <https://github.com/maahn/pyOptimalEstimation>
12. Maahn, M., and D. Ori (2019), Maahn/pamtra2: calibrationPaper_v1, Zenodo, doi:[10.5281/zenodo.2552448](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2552448)
13. Maahn, M. (2019), MASC Snowparticle Images, doi:[10.5439/1497701](https://doi.org/10.5439/1497701)
14. Maahn, M. (2012), IMProToo - Improved Mrr Processing Tool <https://github.com/maahn/IMProToo>

Invited Talks

1. Maahn, M. (2021), What every Meteorologist should know about Inverse Modelling, *Colloquium*, Bern University
2. Maahn, M. (2019), Spatial variability of cloud properties at the North Slope of Alaska, *Colloquium*, Leipzig University
3. Maahn, M. (2019), Spatial variability of cloud properties at the North Slope of Alaska, *Colloquium*, Karlsruhe Institute of Technology
4. Maahn, M. (2018), Anthropogenic pollution and cloud properties at the North Slope of Alaska, *AOS Colloquium*, University of Wisconsin Madison
5. Maahn, M., C. Acquistapace, G. de Boer, C. J. Cox, G. Feingold, T. Marke, and C. R. Williams (2018), Investigating the impact of anthropogenic pollution on cloud properties derived from ground based remote sensors at the North Slope of Alaska, *EGU General Assembly*, Vienna, Austria
6. Maahn, M. (2015), Using vertically pointing Doppler radar to study clouds (and precipitation), *Invited Seminar Talk*, Cooperative Institute for Research in Environmental Sciences, Boulder, CO, USA

Oral conference presentation (first author only)

1. Maahn, M., M. Radenz, C. Cox, M. Gallagher, J. Hutchings, M. Shupe, and T. Uttal (2023), Measuring snowfall properties with the Video In Situ Snowfall Sensor during MOSAiC, *2nd International MOSAiC Science Conference*, Boulder, CO, USA
2. Maahn, M., M. Radenz, C. Cox, M. Gallagher, J. Hutchings, M. Shupe, and T. Uttal (2023), Measuring snowfall properties with the Video In Situ Snowfall Sensor during MOSAiC, *EGU General Assembly*, Vienna, Austria
3. Maahn, M., T. Goren, M. D. Shupe, and G. de Boer (2022), Clouds in Northern Alaska Demonstrate Sensitivity to Local Industrial Aerosol Emissions, *CATCH Open Science Workshop*, online
4. Maahn, M., G. de Boer, C. J. Cox, T. Goren, M. Shupe, and C. R. Williams (2019), Investigating the Impact of Local Anthropogenic Pollution on Cloud Properties at the North Slope of Alaska from Different Perspectives, *AMS - 15th Conference on Polar Meteorology and Oceanography*, Boulder, CO, USA
5. Maahn, M., G. de Boer, C. J. Cox, T. Goren, M. Shupe, and C. R. Williams (2019), Investigating the Impact of Local Anthropogenic Pollution on Cloud Properties at the North Slope of Alaska from Different Perspectives, *1st QuIESCENT Workshop: Quantifying the Indirect Effect: From Sources to Climate Effects of Natural and Transported Aerosol in the Arctic*, Cambridge, United Kingdom
6. Maahn, M., G. de Boer, C. J. Cox, T. Goren, M. Shupe, and C. R. Williams (2019), Investigating the Impact of Local Anthropogenic Pollution on Cloud Properties at the North Slope of Alaska from Different Perspectives, *Gordon Research Conference on Radiation and Climate*, Lewiston, ME, USA

7. Maahn, M., C. Acquistapace, G. de Boer, C. J. Cox, G. Feingold, T. Marke, M. D. Shupe, C. Wiedinmyer, and C. R. Williams (2018), Investigating the Impact of Anthropogenic Pollution on Cloud Properties Derived from Ground Based Remote Sensors at the North Slope of Alaska, *AMS 15th Conference on Cloud Physics & Atmospheric Radiation*, Vancouver, Canada
8. Maahn, M., C. Acquistapace, C. J. Cox, J. M. Creamean, G. de Boer, T. Marke, S. Y. Matrosov, O. Perrson, M. D. Shupe, C. Wiedinmyer, and C. R. Williams (2018), Spatial Dependence of Cloud Properties at Oliktok Point in Northern Alaska AND Anthropogenic pollution and cloud properties at the North Slope of Alaska, *ARM/ASR Joint User Facility PI Meeting*, Vienna, VA, USA
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13. Maahn, M. (2016), How to simulate a radar observation?, in *Atmospheric Radiation Science Workshop*, Boulder, CO, USA
14. Maahn, M., and U. Löhnert (2016), Potential of Higher Moments of the Radar Doppler Spectrum for Studying Ice Clouds, *ARM/ASR Joint User Facility PI Meeting*, Vienna, VA, USA
15. Maahn, M., C. Burgard, S. Crewell, I. V. Gorodetskaya, S. Kneifel, S. Lhermitte, K. Van Tricht, and N. Van Lipzig (2015), Investigating the impact of space-born radar blind zone on surface snowfall statistics in polar regions, *IUGG General Assembly*, Prague, Czech Republic
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18. Maahn, M., U. Löhnert, and P. Kollias (2014), Evaluierung von Eiswolken-Parametrisierungen mittels höheren Radarmomenten, *DPG- Frühjahrstagung*, Berlin, Germany

19. Maahn, M. (2014), Higher Moments of the Doppler Spectrum., *MIRA Millimetre Cloud Radar Workshop*, Munich, Germany
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21. Maahn, M., U. Löhnert, S. Kneifel, and P. Kollias (2013), Combining ground-based active and passive microwave instruments for remote sensing of ice and mixed phase cloud properties, *Davos Atmosphere and Cryosphere Assembly DACA-13*, Davos, Switzerland
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Poster conference presentation (first author only)

1. Maahn, M., D. Moisseev, I. Steinke, N. Maherndl, and M. D. Shupe, (2024), Introducing the Video In Situ Snowfall Sensor for Advancing Radar Retrievals, *12th European conference on RADar in meteorology and hydrology*, Rome.
2. Maahn, M., A. Battaglia, A. Illingworth, P. Kollias, S. Lhermitte, F. E. Scarsi, and F. Tridon (2024), How can the proposed WIVERN satellite mission improve global snowfall measurements?, *EGU General Assembly*, Vienna
3. Maahn, M., D. Moisseev, I. Steinke, N. Maherndl, and M. D. Shupe (2024), Introducing the Video In Situ Snowfall Sensor (VISS), *3rd International MOSAiC Science Conference*, Potsdam
4. Maahn, M., D. Moisseev, I. Steinke, N. Maherndl, and M. D. Shupe (2023), Introducing the Video In Situ Snowfall Sensor (VISS), *4th International Summer Snowfall Workshop*, Leipzig
5. Maahn, M., M. Radenz, C. Cox, M. Gallagher, J. Hutchings, M. Shupe, and T. Uttal (2021), Measuring snowfall properties with the Video In Situ Snowfall Sensor during MOSAiC, *EGU General Assembly*
6. Maahn, M., M. Radenz, C. Cox, M. Gallagher, J. Hutchings, M. Shupe, and T. Uttal (2021), Measuring snowfall properties with the Video In Situ Snowfall Sensor during MOSAiC, *3rd International Summer Snowfall Workshop*, Online
7. Maahn, M., M. D. Shupe, and T. Uttal (2020), First results from a Video In-Situ Snowfall Sensor (VISS) deployed during the MOSAiC campaign, *2020 Polar Technology Conference*, Boulder, CO, USA

8. Maahn, M., C. Cox, G. de Boer, S. Matrosov, M. Shupe, and C. Williams (2019), Northern Alaska Site Science: Instrument Quality and Data Stream Developments, *ARM/ASR Joint User Facility PI Meeting*, Rockville, MA, USA Boulder, CO, USA
9. Maahn, M., G. de Boer, C. J. Cox, T. Goren, M. Shupe, and C. R. Williams (2019), vestigating the Impact of Local Anthropogenic Pollution on Cloud Properties at the North Slope of Alaska from Different Perspectives, *Gordon Research Conference on Radiation and Climate*, Lewiston, ME, USA
10. Maahn, M., G. de Boer, J. M. Creamean, C. J. Cox, S. Y. Matrosov, A. McComiskey, M. D. Shupe, A. Solomon, D. D. Turner, and C. R. Williams (2018), Oliktok Point Site Science: Development of Advanced Observational Perspectives to Aid Model Evaluation, *ARM/ASR Joint User Facility PI Meeting*, Vienna, VA, USA
11. Maahn, M., G. de Boer, S. Y. Matrosov, and T. Goren (2018), Spatial dependence of cloud properties at the North Slope of Alaska, *AGU Fall Meeting*, Washington, D.C
12. Maahn, M., G. de Boer, J. M. Creamean, G. Feingold, M. Norgren, A. Solomon, C. Williams, and W. Wei (2017), Observations and Modeling of Aerosol-Cloud Interactions at ARM Sites in Alaska, *ARM/ASR Joint User Facility PI Meeting*, Vienna, VA, USA
13. Maahn, M., and U. Löhnert (2016), Potential of higher order moments of the radar Doppler spectrum for retrieving microphysical and kinematic properties of Arctic ice clouds, *17th International Conference on Clouds & Precipitation*, Manchester, UK
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17. Maahn, M., U. Löhnert, P. Kollias, R. Jackson, and G. M. McFarquhar (2015), Using higher radar moments to study ice clouds with vertically pointing cloud radars., *ARM/ASR Joint User Facility PI Meeting*, Vienna, VA, USA
18. Maahn, M., U. Löhnert, and P. Kollias (2014), Evaluation of ice cloud parametrisations using higher radar moments, *Atmospheric System Research (ASR) 2014 Science Team Meeting*, Potomac, MD, USA
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20. Maahn, M., and U. Löhnert (2013), Using Higher Radar Moments for Observing Ice Clouds (Sensitivity Study), *Fourth International Workshop on Spacebased Snowfall Measurement*, Mammoth Mountains, CA, USA

Paper I

Can liquid cloud microphysical processes be used for vertically pointing cloud radar calibration?

Maahn, M., Hoffmann, F., Shupe, M. D., de Boer, G., Matrosov, S. Y., and Luke, E. P.: Can Liquid Cloud Microphysical Processes Be Used for Vertically Pointing Cloud Radar Calibration?, *Atmos. Meas. Tech.*, 12, 3151–3171, doi:[10.5194/amt-12-3151-2019](https://doi.org/10.5194/amt-12-3151-2019), 2019

Author contributions: M. Maahn developed the methodology, ran the model, analyzed the data, and drafted the manuscript. F. Hoffmann developed and adapted the model. M. Shupe provided the phase classification. All authors contributed to the methodology, the interpretation of the results, and the editing of the paper.

Paper II

Optimal Estimation Retrievals and Their Uncertainties: What Every Atmospheric Scientist Should Know

Maahn, M., Turner, D. D., Löhnert, U., Posselt, D. J., Ebell, K., Mace, G. G., and Comstock, J. M.: Optimal Estimation Retrievals and Their Uncertainties: What Every Atmospheric Scientist Should Know, *Bull. Am. Meteorol. Soc.*, 101, E1512–E1523, doi:[10.1175/BAMS-D-19-0027.1](https://doi.org/10.1175/BAMS-D-19-0027.1), 2020

Author contributions: The study was designed by M. Maahn and D. Turner with contributions from all authors. M. Maahn developed the Python library, wrote the supporting Jupyter Notebooks, analyzed the examples cases, did all but one figure, and drafted the majority of the manuscript. D. Turner created Figure 1 and drafted the introduction. All authors reviewed and edited the draft.

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Paper III

Introducing the Video In Situ Snowfall Sensor (VISSS)

Maahn, M., Moisseev, D., Steinke, I., Maherndl, N., and Shupe, M. D.: Introducing the Video In Situ Snowfall Sensor (VISSS), *Atmos. Meas. Tech.*, 17, 899–919, doi:[10.5194/amt-17-899-2024](https://doi.org/10.5194/amt-17-899-2024), 2024

Author contributions: M. Maahn acquired funding, developed the instrument, processed the VISSS data, analyzed the data of the case study, and wrote the manuscript. D. Moisseev processed PIP and Parsivel data and contributed to data analysis. N. Maherndl and I. Steinke contributed to instrument calibration and particle tracking development, respectively. M. Shupe supported funding acquisition and was responsible for the VISSS deployment at MOSAiC. All authors reviewed and edited the draft.

Paper IV

The observed influence of local anthropogenic pollution on northern Alaskan cloud properties

Maahn, M., de Boer, G., Creamean, J. M., Feingold, G., McFarquhar, G. M., Wu, W., and Mei, F.: The Observed Influence of Local Anthropogenic Pollution on Northern Alaskan Cloud Properties, *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 17, 14 709–14 726, doi:[10.5194/acp-17-14709-2017](https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-17-14709-2017), 2017

Author contributions: The study was designed by M. Maahn and G. de Boer with contributions from all authors. M. Maahn analyzed the data, created the figures, and drafted the manuscript. G. de Boer acquired funding. J. Creamean supported the analysis of the aerosol data, G. Feingold supported quantifying the aerosol effects. G. McFarquhar, W. Wu, and F. Mei processed in situ cloud observations and assisted with their use. All authors reviewed and edited the draft.

Paper V

Liquid Containing Clouds at the North Slope of Alaska Demonstrate Sensitivity to Local Industrial Aerosol Emissions

Maahn, M., Goren, T., Shupe, M. D., and de Boer, G.: Liquid Containing Clouds at the North Slope of Alaska Demonstrate Sensitivity to Local Industrial Aerosol Emissions, *Geophys. Res. Lett.*, 48, e2021GL094307, doi:[10.1029/2021GL094307](https://doi.org/10.1029/2021GL094307), 2021

Author contributions: The study was designed by M. Maahn with contributions from all authors. M. Maahn analyzed the data, created the figures, and drafted the manuscript. T. Goren supported the MODIS data analysis. G. de Boer acquired funding. G. de Boer and M. Shupe supported the interpretation of the results. All authors reviewed and edited the draft.

Paper VI

Using artificial neural networks to predict riming from Doppler cloud radar observations

Vogl, T., Maahn, M., Kneifel, S., Schimmel, W., Moisseev, D., and Kalesse-Los, H.: Using Artificial Neural Networks to Predict Riming from Doppler Cloud Radar Observations, *Atmos. Meas. Tech.*, 15, 365–381, doi:[10.5194/amt-15-365-2022](https://doi.org/10.5194/amt-15-365-2022), 2022

Author contributions: The method was developed by T. Vogl, M. Maahn, and H. Kalesse-Los with contributions by all co-authors. S. Kneifel provided the RIPEXPOL data set, D. Moisseev the in situ data for the BAECC data set, and M. Maahn the in situ data for the Leipzig data set. T. Vogl performed data visualization and analysis, with help from all co-authors. The text was written by T. Vogl and reviewed by all co-authors.

Paper VII

A riming-dependent parameterization of scattering by snowflakes using the self-similar Rayleigh–Gans approximation

Maherndl, N., Maahn, M., Tridon, F., Leinonen, J., Ori, D., and Kneifel, S.: A Riming-Dependent Parameterization of Scattering by Snowflakes Using the Self-Similar Rayleigh–Gans Approximation, *Q. J. R. Meteorolog. Soc.*, 149, 3562–3581, doi:[10.1002/qj.4573](https://doi.org/10.1002/qj.4573), 2023

Author contributions: N. Maherndl: conceptualization; formal analysis; methodology; visualization; writing – original draft; writing – review and editing. M. Maahn: conceptualization; funding acquisition; supervision; writing – review and editing. F. Tridon: conceptualization; software; writing – review and editing. J. Leinonen: software; writing – review and editing. D. Ori: software; writing – review and editing. S. Kneifel: conceptualization; writing – review and editing.

Paper VIII

Quantifying Riming from Airborne Data during the HALO-(AC)³ Campaign

Maherndl, N., Moser, M., Lucke, J., Mech, M., Risse, N., Schirmacher, I., and Maahn, M.: Quantifying Riming from Airborne Data during the HALO-(AC)³ Campaign, *Atmos. Meas. Tech.*, 17, 1475–1495, doi:[10.5194/amt-17-1475-2024](https://doi.org/10.5194/amt-17-1475-2024), 2024a

Author contributions: N. Maherndl developed the described methods to quantify riming, analyzed and plotted the data, and wrote the paper. M. Maahn acquired funding and supervised the research project. M. Moser collected and processed CDP, CIP, and PIP data and provided combined size distributions. J. Luke collected and processed Nevzorov probe data. M. Mech and N. Risse collected and processed MiRAC-A data and retrieved the LWP product. M. Mech, N. Risse, and I. Schirmacher collected and processed AMALi data and retrieved the CTH product. All authors reviewed and edited the draft.

Paper IX

How does riming influence the observed spatial variability of ice water in mixed-phase clouds?

Maherndl, N., Moser, M., Schirmacher, I., Bansemer, A., Lucke, J., Voigt, C., and Maahn, M.: How Does Riming Influence the Observed Spatial Variability of Ice Water in Mixed-Phase Clouds?, *EGUsph.* (in review for *ACP*), pp. 1–38, doi:[10.5194/egusphere-2024-1214](https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-2024-1214), 2024b

Author contributions: N. Maherndl conceptualized the study, analyzed and plotted the data, and wrote the paper. M. Maahn contributed to the concept, acquired funding, and supervised the research project. M. Moser and C. Voigt collected and processed CDP, CIP, and PIP data during HALO-(AC)³ and provided combined size distributions. J. Lucke collected and processed Nevzorov probe data during HALO-(AC)³. I. Schirmacher collected and processed AMALi data during HALO-(AC)³ and retrieved the CTH product. A. Bansemer collected and processed CDP, Fast-CDP, 2D-S, and HVPS-3 data during IMPACTS and provided combined size distributions. All authors reviewed and edited the draft.

Paper X

New insights into ice multiplication using remote-sensing observations of slightly supercooled mixed-phase clouds in the Arctic

Luke, E. P., Yang, F., Kollias, P., Vogelmann, A. M., and Maahn, M.: New Insights into Ice Multiplication Using Remote-Sensing Observations of Slightly Supercooled Mixed-Phase Clouds in the Arctic, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.*, 118, doi:[10.1073/pnas.2021387118](https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2021387118), 2021

Author contributions: E. Luke, F. Yang, P. Kollias, A. Vogelmann, and M. Maahn designed research; E. Luke, F. Yang, P. Kollias, and A. Vogelmann performed research; E. Luke, F. Yang, P. Kollias, and A. Vogelmann analyzed data; and E. Luke, F. Yang, P. Kollias, A. Vogelmann, and M. Maahn wrote the paper.

